

Best Practice Guidelines

Edited by:
Manuel Conde-Cid,
Paula Pérez-Rodríguez and
David Fernández-Calviño

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Best Management Practices Guidelines Manual

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Edited by Manuel Conde-Cid, Paula Pérez-Rodríguez and David Fernández-Calviño (Universidade de Vigo – UVigo).

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Introduction

Food security is the cornerstone of human health and economic stability. In this context, ensuring access to safe, nutritious, and affordable food is crucial for the sustenance and proper development of the global population (Goel et al., 2024). To date, in order to increase crop yields and meet the food demands of a growing population, European agriculture has relied on monoculture, intensive mechanisation, and the excessive use of external inputs such as pesticides and fertilisers. These practices have tended to replace the biological functions that were initially fulfilled by the biodiversity of agricultural soils. While enhancing crop yields, these intensive agricultural systems have also led to numerous associated side effects, such as soil contamination and degradation, aquatic ecosystem pollution, biodiversity loss, an increase in the incidence of diseases and pests, and higher greenhouse gas emissions, among others. Consequently, this has led to a decline in soil ecosystem services and a reduction in the long-term sustainability of agricultural systems, posing a significant threat to food security and representing a major economic risk to farmers (Rehman et al., 2022; Boix-Fayos and de Vente, 2023; Hokkanen, 2024; Dunn et al., 2025).

In light of this, it is crucial to transition from conventional intensive agriculture to more stable and sustainable farming systems. In this regard, the European Union has recently introduced the “Farm to Fork” strategy as one of the main pillars of the European Green Deal, aiming to establish a resilient food system that is better suited to the future, while ensuring minimal environmental impact and more equitable economic profitability for farmers (European Commission, 2019).

To achieve this transition, it is crucial to consider soil biodiversity. In this sense, both microorganisms and other soil organisms play a key role in agricultural systems, performing multiple functions that contribute to the decomposition and mineralisation of organic matter, pest and disease control, soil structure improvement, more efficient and sustainable nutrient cycling, and carbon capture and storage, among others (Dunn et al., 2025). As a result, soil biodiversity determines fertility, productivity, and stress tolerance (Hartmann and Six, 2023), thereby reducing dependence on external inputs and enhancing the resilience of agricultural systems, contributing to their long-term sustainability. However, current intensive agricultural systems are causing a reduction in the diversity and abundance of multiple soil organism groups, thus posing a threat to soil health and the long-term sustainability of agriculture (Cozim-Melges et al., 2025).

Given this, it is necessary to adopt new agricultural management practices and cropping systems that enhance the genetic and functional biodiversity of the soil to reduce the use of inputs (fertilisers and pesticides), while simultaneously increasing crop yield and quality, soil ecosystem services, and agricultural stability and resilience.

Therefore, the SoildiverAgro project aimed to provide a solid scientific understanding of the impacts of different sustainable management practices and cropping systems

on improving soil biodiversity, as well as how this relates to crop performance and quality, along with other ecosystem services such as fertility and carbon sequestration. Furthermore, all of this should lead to an increase in farmers' income and an improvement in the competitiveness of European agriculture in the global market.

More specifically, the project evaluated how cropping systems that promote soil biodiversity can: a) effectively enhance genetic and functional microbial diversity, with reductions in soil-borne diseases; b) increase the diversity of biological regulators and ecosystem engineers, such as nematodes and earthworms; c) reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, while improving crop yields; d) improve food quality; e) enhance soil fertility through nutrient retention, preventing leaching and increasing plant cover, thus reducing soil erosion; f) improve soil structure and quality, increase carbon sequestration, support natural soil functioning, and promote the formation of stable aggregates that enhance water infiltration, root penetration, and soil water retention; g) optimise the use of fertilisers and pesticides; and h) reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

To achieve this, field experiments were conducted, establishing 17 case studies across six different pedoclimatic regions in Europe (Mediterranean South, Lusitanian, Atlantic Central, Continental, Nemoral, and Boreal). These experiments allowed for testing the benefits and drawbacks of different alternative sustainable cropping systems, with the potential to foster soil biodiversity, in comparison with the conventional systems and management practices of each region. For each case study, various challenges were identified, such as production costs, pest or disease incidence, nutrient availability, low soil quality, and soil or water pollution. These challenges can be minimised through effective soil biodiversity management. Consequently, the objective of all the case studies was to promote soil biodiversity to address current agronomic, economic, and environmental issues, but tackled through diverse management practices and cropping systems tailored to each specific challenge, as well as the agronomic, economic, environmental, social, and cultural characteristics.

Manuel Conde-Cid^{ab}, Paula Pérez-Rodríguez^{ab}, David Fernández-Calviño^{ab}

^aSection for Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Department of Plant Biology and Soil Science, Faculty of Sciences, University of Vigo, As Lagoas s/n, Ourense 32004, Spain

^bInstitute of Agroecology and Food (IAA), Universidade de Vigo – Campus Auga, Ourense 32004, Spain

Case study 1

Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region

Use of soil biodiversity to reduce soil-borne diseases/ pests incidence and increase nutrient availability in potatoes cropped in multiple cropping and rotations

Irene Ollio^{ab}, Eva Lloret^{ab}, Silvia Martínez-Martínez^a, Josefina Contreras^a, Raúl Zornoza^{ab}, Catalina Egea^{ab}, Juan Fernández^{ab}

^aDepartment of Agricultural Engineering, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Paseo Alfonso XIII 48, Cartagena 30203, Spain

^bInstitute of Plant Biotechnology, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Plaza del Hospital s/n, Cartagena 30202, Spain

1.1.

Study location

Case study 1 (CS1) is located in Cartagena, in Southeast Spain, at the Tomás Ferro Experimental Farm of the Polytechnic University of Cartagena (UPCT), Spain (37°41'16.6"N 0°56'55.6"W) (Fig. 1).

The climate is semiarid Mediterranean, with a mean annual precipitation of 300 mm and a mean annual temperature of 18°C. Annual potential evapotranspiration exceeds 1,200 mm.

The soil is classified as Haplic Calcisol (loamic, hypercalcic) [IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022], with a clay loam texture, 1.8% organic matter, 25.2% of CaCO_3 , and a pH of 8.2.

The experimental farm is located in a region dedicated to intensive horticulture, where multiple cropping (winter and summer crops) is adopted to increase profitability, along with crop rotations to avoid issues associated with monocropping.

The main crops grown are lettuce, cabbage, spinach, broccoli, celery, melon, watermelon, and potato.

The primary environmental challenges in the area include low biodiversity both below and above ground, soil erosion, low soil organic matter content, weak soil structure, low nutrient availability, and excessive use of water and nutrients.

Fig. 1. Experimental plots (left) and CS1 location (right).

1.2.

Management practices implemented

During the three years of experimentation, the following crops were rotated in case study 1 (Fig. 2):

1. Potato, from 22 December 2020 to 4 June 2021.
2. Broccoli, from 5 October 2021 to 10 January 2022.
3. Melon, from 29 March 2022 to 14 July 2022.
4. Potato, from 16 December 2022 to 15 May 2023.

Fig. 2. Management practices implemented and a representation of the objectives aimed to be achieved.

Following the local practices, the crops were established under drip irrigation and mineral fertilization. Four different fertilization treatments were designed, in which the mineral fertilizer was reduced to partially replace it with biostimulants:

1. Mineral fertilizers applied at the nutritional demands of the crop (**F100**).
2. 50% of the rate of mineral fertilizers added in F100 (**F50**).
3. F50 + application of biostimulants (a formulation of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacteria (**BAI**)).
4. F50 + application of biostimulants (a formulation of bacteria and non-mycorrhizal fungi (**BAI+FU**)).

The formulation of BAI was mostly based on plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) such as *Azospirillum*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Bacillus* (Bactoneco®). The formulation of BAI+FU was mostly based on a mix of PGPR such as *Bacillus* and *Azotobacter*, and beneficial non-mycorrhizal fungi (Nuve®). These products were provided by "Fertilizantes y Nutrientes Ecológicos S.L." (Spain), and the exact compositions were not shared due to the protection of the providers' intellectual property rights.

The field experiment was established as a completely randomized design with four treatments, each covering 740 m², and composed of four replicates. All treatments received the same quantity of irrigation, which was scheduled according to the climatic conditions, crop coefficient, and evapotranspiration rate. In all treatments, the soil was tilled at 25 cm depth for crop preparation.

1.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

1. The addition of biostimulants did not increase crop yields in any crops, but kept yields at the same level as full mineral fertilization.
2. The addition of biostimulants did not affect broccoli and melon quality, although it improved potato quality. However, size distribution and starch content showed no significant differences between treatments. BAI+FU showed the highest mean weight and flesh firmness of tubers. In addition, the addition of BAI+FU reduced the incidence of *Rhizoctonia* in tubers compared to full mineral fertilization by 50%, improving the marketable value of the potatoes.
3. Soil CO₂ emissions were reduced by 40% when adding biostimulants compared to full mineral fertilization.
4. The application of biofertilizers enhanced N fixation, ammonification, denitrification, and CO₂ fixation, compared to full mineral fertilization, leading to increased availability of nutrients, despite reducing the external addition of them through fertilization.
5. There was an increase in prokaryote diversity with the addition of biostimulants, with changes in the taxonomic composition. However, the use of biostimulants did not affect the overall fungal diversity and composition. There was a decrease in the abundance of fungal pathogens and an increase in the relative abundance of fungal symbiotrophs in BAI+FU.
6. The number and biodiversity of nematodes were not affected by the addition of biostimulants, but their composition changed compared to full mineral fertilization. In addition, the addition of biostimulants led to a decreased functional complexity of the nematode community, increasing nematode taxa that feed on bacteria and fungi.
7. The addition of biostimulants had no impact on economic revenues, production costs and farm gross margins. This is because the savings in fertilizer costs from the reduced fertilization rate offset the cost of biostimulants.

In the case of a farm dedicated to intensive horticulture in the Mediterranean basin, the partial replacement (50%) of mineral fertilizers with biostimulants could be promoted. This is especially true when plant growth-promoting bacteria and fungi are applied together. Such an approach helps reduce the dependency on mineral fertilizers, while stimulating beneficial microorganisms that contribute to maintaining high crop yields and reducing soil pathogen abundance and incidence, with no increase in production costs and the maintenance of gross margins.

This will result in the following benefits:

- High crop yields.
- Reduced soil CO₂ emissions.
- Improved potato quality.
- Reduced abundance and incidence of pathogens in potato.
- Increased soil bacterial diversity, with increased soil functioning (higher nutrient availability for plant uptake).

Biostimulants are added through the irrigation system as fertigation, just as done for fertilizers. Thus, no extra investment in equipment is needed.

1.4.

Potential drawbacks

No drawbacks were observed in this case study with the addition of both biostimulants, with no negative environmental, agronomic, or economic effects compared to full mineral fertilization.

Case study 2

Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region

Use of soil biodiversity to increase nutrient and water availability and reduce soil- borne diseases incidence to increase wheat yields

Irene Ollio^{ab}, Eva Lloret^{ab}, Silvia Martínez-Martínez^a, Josefina Contreras^a, Raúl Zornoza^{ab}, Catalina Egea^{ab}, Juan Fernández^{ab}

^aDepartment of Agricultural Engineering, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Paseo Alfonso XIII 48, Cartagena 30203, Spain

^bInstitute of Plant Biotechnology, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Plaza del Hospital s/n, Cartagena 30202, Spain

2.1.

Study location

Case study 2 (CS2) was carried out in the Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region (Spain), specifically on the farm La Junquera, in the Region of Murcia (Southeast of Spain) (37°56'11.2"N 2°10'11.2"W) (Fig. 3).

The climate is semiarid Mediterranean, with a mean annual precipitation of 316 mm and a mean annual temperature of 13°C. Annual potential evapotranspiration exceeds 1,000 mm.

The soil is classified as Calcic Cambisol [IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022], with a

clay texture, organic matter content of 2.3%, CaCO₃ content of 49%, and a pH of 9.0.

The commercial farm is located in a region dedicated to field crops, mostly cereals such as wheat, barley, or rye, with the adoption of rotations to avoid problems related to monocropping.

The most important environmental problems are low below and aboveground biodiversity, soil erosion, low soil organic matter content, weak soil structure, and low availability of nutrients and water.

Fig. 3. Experimental plots (left) and CS1 location (right).

2.2.

Management practices implemented

During the three years of experimentation, we rotated in case study 2 the following crops (Fig. 4):

1. Rye, from 12 December 2020 to 29 July 2021.
2. Wheat, from 1 December 2021 to 3 August 2022.
3. Ervil, sown on 1 December 2022, but crop could not develop due to extreme drought during winter/spring 2023.

Fig. 4. Management practices implemented and a representation of the objectives aimed to be achieved.

Following the local practices, the crops were established under drip irrigation and mineral fertilization. Four different fertilization treatments were designed, in which mineral fertilizer was reduced to be partially replaced by biostimulants:

1. Mineral fertilizers applied at the nutritional demands of the crop (**F100**).
2. 70% of the rate of mineral fertilizers added in F70 (**F50**).
3. F70 + the application of biostimulants (a formulation of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacteria (**BAI**)).
4. F70 + the application of biostimulants (a formulation of bacteria and non-mycorrhizal fungi (**BAI+FU**)).

The formulation of BAI was mostly based on plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) such as *Azospirillum*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Bacillus* (Bactoneco®). The formulation of BAI+FU was mostly based on a mix of PGPR such as *Bacillus* and *Azotobacter*, and beneficial non-mycorrhizal fungi (Nuve®). These products were provided by "Fertilizantes y Nutrientes Ecológicos S.L." (Spain), and the exact compositions were not shared due to the protection of the providers' intellectual property rights.

The field experiment was established in one block with the four treatments of 1.1 ha each. True field replication was impossible owing to machinery and labor constraints in the commercial farm. In all treatments, the soil was tilled at 25 cm depth for the preparation of the crop.

2.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

- The addition of biostimulants did not increase crop yields in any crops, but kept yields at the same level of full mineral fertilization. Crop quality was not affected by the addition of biostimulants.
- There was no effect of biostimulants on soil organic carbon sequestration and storage, nutrients availability, and prokaryotic, fungal and nematode diversity and composition.
- Functional gene abundance for genes involved in the C and N cycles was not affected by biostimulants either, indicating no changes in the functional diversity of the soil microbiota.
- Biostimulants addition led to decreased functional complexity of the nematode community, increasing nematode taxa that feed on bacteria and fungi.
- The 30% reduction in organic fertilization (F70) increased nematode diversity, with similar prokaryote and fungal community structure and diversity, soil organic matter level and nutrient availability for plant uptake compared to full organic fertilization.
- The addition of biostimulants had a high negative impact on farm gross margins (-52%), related to the high cost of biostimulants, with increased production costs (+31%), and no effect on revenues.
- Interestingly, the fertilization decrease by 30% contributed to the same crop yields as full fertilization, with the same revenues and an increase in gross margins by 56% owing to savings in fertilization costs.

In the case of a farm dedicated to organic rainfed field crops in the Mediterranean basin, organic fertilization could be reduced with no negative effect on crop yield and quality, and on soil health, increasing nematode diversity. The use of biofertilizers was not successful in increasing productivity nor soil biodiversity or multifunctionality.

This will result in the following benefits:

- Increased gross margins due to decreased production costs.
- No negative effect on crop yields.
- Increased nematode diversity with no negative effects on soil microbial diversity and soil fertility, at least in the short-term.

2.4.

Potential drawbacks

Owing to the high price of commercial biostimulants, this strategy may not be competitive for rainfed organic systems under the Mediterranean climate, since there is no increase in crop yields and quality.

Case study 3

Lusitanian pedoclimatic region

Use of crop diversification and trap crops in potato fields

Manuel Conde-Cid^{ab}, Paula Pérez-Rodríguez^{ab}, David Fernández-Calviño^{ab}

^aSection for Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Department of Plant Biology and Soil Science, Faculty of Sciences, University of Vigo, As Lagoas s/n, Ourense 32004, Spain

^bInstitute of Agroecology and Food (IAA), Universidade de Vigo – Campus Auga, Ourense 32004, Spain

3.1.

Study location

Case study 3 (CS3) was carried out in the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region (Spain), specifically in the Limia region, where potatoes are the primary crop, conventionally rotated with cereals (wheat). The area has a high incidence of cyst nematode infestations. As a result, the use of nematicides is considerable, which increases production costs and contributes to soil and water pollution. Furthermore, both aboveground and belowground biodiversity are limited, primarily due to the extensive application of agricultural inputs.

The experimental plots are in the town of Sandiás, located within the province of Ourense, in the Galicia autonomous community (Fig. 5). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots involved in this case study are $42^{\circ}6'0.32''\text{N}$, $7^{\circ}43'29.98''\text{W}$. The location is characterised by a mean annual temperature of 12.9°C , mean annual precipitation of 780 mm, and an annual potential evapotranspiration of 2.9 mm.

Fig. 5. CS3 location (above) and experimental plot (below).

3.2.

Management practices implemented

Case study 3 explores the potential of using appropriate crop diversification to increase soil biodiversity and, together with the management of trap crops in potato fields, to reduce the incidence of cyst nematodes. This strategy involves enhancing soil biodiversity and reducing nematicide use, thereby promoting sustainable and profitable potato production practices.

Therefore, the new management practices implemented in this area included the diversification of crop rotations and the introduction of a trap crop (together with the analysis of best conditions for its implementation). These practices were carried out between 2021 and 2023. The objectives were to develop management practices allowing to reduce the incidence of cyst nematodes, thereby decreasing the use of nematicides, and external nitrogen fertilisation, as well as to enhance crop yields and soil biodiversity (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Management practices implemented and a representation of the objectives aimed to be achieved.

Case study 3 was composed by two different experiments:

- **Experiment 1:** best conditions for trap crop (*Solanum sisymbriifolium*) emergence and development. Crop planting date and depth of sowing were evaluated together with two auxiliary parameters (soil compaction and irrigation). The effectiveness of *Solanum sisymbriifolium* on cyst incidence was also tested on infested fields.
- **Experiment 2:** crop diversification. The experimental design comprised three different crop rotations, as outlined in Table 1. The treatments were applied as follows:
 1. The control treatment involved conventional management practices with a typical crop rotation (potato-cereal-potato) (**Ctrl**).
 2. Crop diversification, including a leguminous (peas) in the rotation to naturally fix N in the soil and reduce inputs application (cereal – legume (peas) – potato) (**Alt1Pot**, alternative crop rotation 1 in the potato field).
 3. Trap crop (*Solanum sisymbriifolium*) inclusion in the rotation plus a cover crop (vetch/oats) (**Alt2Pot**, alternative crop rotation 2 in the potato field).

Table 1. Composition of each type rotation including the period of application.

Crop rotation	Cycle 1		Cycle 2	Cycle 3
Ctrl	Potatoes		Cereal (wheat)	Potatoes
	MAY - SEP 21		OCT 21 - JUL 22	MAY - SEP 23
Alt1Pot	Cereal (wheat)		Leguminous (peas)	Potatoes
	APR - JUL 21		APR - JUL 22	MAY - SEP 23
Alt2Pot	Potatoes	Cover Crop (Vetch/Oats)	Trap crop	Potatoes
	APR - SEP 21	NOV - AUG 22	AUG - NOV 22	MAY - SEP 23

3.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Solanum sisymbriifolium yielded satisfactory results, demonstrating high effectiveness in reducing potato cyst nematodes (*Globodera* spp.) and consequently, leading to a reduction in the use of chemically synthesized nematicides. Fig. 7 presents the results obtained in the experiments carried out in 2022,

as published in Gómez-Armesto et al. (2025). Fig. 7a–c display the results from three plots where the trap crop was cultivated (Bustelo – Fig. 7a, Piñeira 1 – Fig. 7b, and Piñeira 2 – Fig. 7c), while Fig. 7d shows the results from a plot located in the same area where *Solanum sisymbriifolium* was not grown.

Fig. 7. Initial N°/cysts (green) and final N°/cysts (yellow) in the three plots studied: Bustelo (a; samples 1B–8B), Piñeira 1 (b; samples 1P–8P), Piñeira 2 (c; samples 1C–6C), and in a plot located in the same area without *Solanum sisymbriifolium* crop (d: samples 1D–8D). Bars indicate standard deviation.

As can be seen, for Bustelo (Fig. 7a) and Piñeira 1 (Fig. 7b), the reduction in the number of nematodes after 13 and 12 weeks of *S. sisymbriifolium* growth was 77% and 89%, respectively. Moreover, in the Piñeira 1 plot, some of the sampled points achieved complete potato cyst nematode elimination, with a 100% reduction. However, in the case of Piñeira 2, the average percentage reduction was 29%, much lower than in the other two plots. This was primarily attributed to poor germination of *S. sisymbriifolium* in this plot, resulting in poor plant growth. **This highlights the critical importance of adequate sowing for achieving high efficiency in reducing cyst nematodes.** Finally, Fig. 7d shows the results obtained from a plot located in the same area without the *S. sisymbriifolium* crop.

In this case, the nematode numbers decreased by between 13% and 20% compared to the initial situation. Therefore, this much smaller reduction in nematode numbers in the plot without the *S. sisymbriifolium* crop, in comparison with the plots containing *S. sisymbriifolium*, confirms the high effectiveness of this trap crop in reducing nematode numbers.

In addition to reducing plant-parasitic nematodes, the incorporation of the trap crop into the rotation system, together with

a winter cover crop (vetch/oats) before *S. sisymbriifolium*, also promotes soil biodiversity and fosters a more active and efficient microbial ecosystem in terms of nutrient recycling. In fact, this treatment also resulted in a 16% increase in the total organic carbon content of the soil, compared to the control (conventional) treatment, thereby promoting carbon sequestration. Similarly, it also led to an average increase of 16% in the total nitrogen content, thereby improving soil fertility.

Regarding economic viability, it was found that the direct cost of wheat cultivation was 2853.48 €/ha, while the cost of the cover crop + trap crop was significantly lower (1907.71 €/ha). However, the income from both crops was very similar (749.95 €/ha for wheat and 770.79 €/ha for the vetch/oats if harvest). Therefore, the economic profitability is negative for both options. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that the loss is much smaller in the case of the cover crop + trap crop (-1044.42 €/ha) compared to wheat (-2013.53 €/ha). Additionally, the trap crop offers the important benefit of significantly reducing nematode cyst numbers, thereby enabling the maintenance of adequate potato production in the long term and preventing the farm from being placed under quarantine due to a high presence of nematodes.

Benefits of Implementing the Trap Crop

In the case of a farm being infested with nematodes, it is strongly recommended to replace wheat with *S. sisymbriifolium* (trap crop) in the crop rotation.

This will result in the following benefits:

- **Natural elimination of nematodes**, thereby reducing the need for chemical synthetic nematicides, thus reducing associated costs and environmental impact.
- **Reduction in direct cultivation costs.**
- **Enhanced soil biodiversity.**
- **Increase in soil fertility.**
- **Increase in C sequestration.**

Recommendations for Implementing the Trap Crops

The best conditions for cropping *S. sisymbriifolium* (trap crop) in South Atlantic latitudes included sowing dates in July and August at a depth of 10–15 cm, with irrigation and soil compaction after sowing. Taking these conditions into account is crucial for good germination and plant development. In this regard, intense and continuous rainfall, along with low temperatures during the germination period, can lead to weak plant growth, making them unable to compete with other weeds. Further information on the optimal conditions for *S. sisymbriifolium* cultivation can be found in Gómez–Armesto et al. (2025).

It is also worth noting that a cereal seeding machine is suitable for sowing *S. sisymbriifolium*, and no specific machinery is required.

Regarding the AltIPot treatment, which involved the inclusion of a leguminous crop (peas) in the rotation, the results obtained were highly satisfactory, as it was observed that the introduced legume effectively fixed nitrogen (N) in the soil. Compared to the conventional treatment, the incorporation of peas led to an average increase of 35% in the soil NH_4^+ content. Furthermore, it was noted that the introduction of the legume resulted in an increased abundance of genes involved in carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles. In fact, alongside the significant increase in ammonium content, a 28% average increase in nitrate (NO_3^-) content was also observed.

This N fixation by the legumes (peas) allowed for a 50% reduction in cover fertilisation during the subsequent potato cropping cycle, compared to the conventional treatment (Ctrl), where wheat had been planted. Moreover, despite halving the cover fertilisation, the potato yield obtained in the legume treatment (AltIPot) was,

on average, 21% higher than that obtained with the conventional treatment, which involved wheat in the rotation. Specifically, with the AltIPot treatment, the average potato yield was 40,283 kg/ha, whereas with the conventional treatment (Ctrl), the average yield was 33,319 kg/ha.

Regarding economic viability, a higher gross margin was achieved for the legume crop (in this case, peas) compared to the cereal crop (in this case, wheat). Although the income from the cereal (749.95 €/ha) was significantly higher than that from the legume (190.50 €/ha), the direct costs associated with growing the legume (1,563.05 €/ha) were considerably lower than those for the cereal (2,853.48 €/ha). Therefore, the results indicate that the losses incurred with the legume crop are substantially smaller than those observed with the cereal crop. Specifically, the legume crop recorded a gross margin of -1,349.69 €/ha, while the gross margin for the cereal crop was -2,013.53 €/ha.

Benefits of Introducing the Leguminous Crop

It is strongly recommended to replace the cereal crop (wheat) with a leguminous crop (peas) in the rotation. This will result in the following benefits:

- Increased potato production in the subsequent cycle.
- Reduction in direct cultivation costs.
- Enhanced soil biodiversity.
- Natural nitrogen fixation, halving the need for external nitrogen input for cover fertilisation, thereby reducing associated costs and environmental impact.
- Increasing gross margins.

Recommendations for Introducing the Leguminous Crop

There are no specific recommendations for implementing this management practice; it simply requires replacing the cereal crop with a leguminous crop. Additionally, a standard cereal seeding machine can be used for sowing the leguminous crop, so no specialized machinery is needed.

3.4.

Potential drawbacks

The only potential drawback is that, in certain years, the necessary climatic conditions may not occur to cultivate *S. sisymbriifolium* successfully, which could result in a low reduction of the cyst nematode. This would be particularly true in years when intense rainfall episodes occur during the months of July and August.

Case study 4

Lusitanian pedoclimatic region

Use of mycorrhizas in potato fields to reduce the incidence on the common scab, decrease the use of phosphorus fertilizers, increase crop yields and soil biodiversity

Manuel Conde-Cid^{ab}, Paula Pérez-Rodríguez^{ab}, David Fernández-Calviño^{ab}

^aSection for Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Department of Plant Biology and Soil Science, Faculty of Sciences, University of Vigo, As Lagoas s/n, Ourense 32004, Spain

^bInstitute of Agroecology and Food (IAA), Universidade de Vigo – Campus Auga, Ourense 32004, Spain

4.1. Study location

Case study 4 (CS4) was carried out in the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region of Spain, specifically in a cropland covering 9.6 hectares in the town of Xinzo de Limia, in the province of Ourense, Galicia (Fig. 8). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots used for this case study are 42° 5' 37.09" N, 7° 41' 52.92" W. This location has a mean annual temperature of 12.9 °C, an average annual precipitation of 780 mm, and an annual potential evapotranspiration of 2.9 mm.

Fig. 8. CS4 location (to the left) and experimental plot (to the right).

4.2.

Management practices implemented

This area is highly affected by common scab, a soil-borne disease caused by the bacterium-like organism *Streptomyces scabies*. This disease significantly impacts potato crops in soils with elevated organic matter content. Therefore, cultivation must be undertaken under strongly acidic conditions (pH <5.0) to limit its spread. Under such conditions, the availability of phosphorus (P) is markedly reduced, despite the presence of high concentrations of phosphorus in the soil. Consequently, farmers apply substantial amounts of synthetic P fertilisers. Furthermore, the diversity of microorganisms and soil fauna is generally low in strongly acidic soils. Common scab impairs the visual quality of potatoes, and hence they are suitable only for industrial processing rather than direct commercial sale, thereby diminishing their economic value.

Fig. 9. Management practices implemented and a representation of the objectives pursued.

Case study 4 explores the potential of introducing mycorrhizas into potato cultivation. Mycorrhizal fungi establish mutually beneficial relationships with plants, providing reciprocal advantages to one another. While plants provide them with sugars, mycorrhizas facilitate the uptake of water and nutrients from the rhizosphere, as well as enhancing plant defence mechanisms against pathogens. Therefore, the aims of Case study 4 were to reduce the incidence of common scab and, consequently, to increase the market value of potatoes; and to slightly raise soil pH and phosphorus (P) availability, thereby reducing the need for external P fertilisation, while increasing crop yield and soil biodiversity (Fig. 9). These practices were implemented between 2021 and 2023.

To achieve these aims, five treatments were tested (Table 2):

- Control with a conventional rotation: potatoes – barley (**Ctrl**).
- Introduction of mycorrhizae into potato cycles, with phosphorus (P) fertilisation reduced by half (**MycPotHP**).
- Introduction of mycorrhizae into potato cycles, with no P fertilisation applied (**MycNoP**).
- Conventional rotation with P fertilisation reduced by half, without mycorrhizae (**PotHP**).
- Conventional rotation without P fertilisation and without mycorrhizae (**PotNoP**).

Table 2. Composition of each type of rotation including the period of application.

Crop rotation	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3
CONTROL (Ctrl)	Potatoes	Cereal (barley)	Potatoes
MYCORRHIZA + ½ P (MycPotHP)	Potatoes + mycorrhiza + ½ P	Cereal (barley)	Potatoes + mycorrhiza + ½ P
MYCORRHIZA + NO P (MycNoP)	Potatoes + mycorrhiza + no P	Cereal (barley)	Potatoes + mycorrhiza + No P
NO MYCORRHIZA + ½ P (PotHP)	Potatoes + ½ P	Cereal (barley)	Potatoes + ½ P
NO MYCORRHIZA + NO P (PotNoP)	Potatoes (No P)	Cereal (barley)	Potatoes (No P)

4.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

The introduction of mycorrhizas did not provide positive results in reducing the incidence of common scab in the two cultivated cycles tested. Similarly, the availability of phosphorus (P) was not significantly affected either by the introduction of mycorrhizas or by the reduction of external P application. This was probably due to the fact that the available P in the soil of this area was already very high (> 150 mg/kg). Therefore, the external application of P is not necessary in the short- to medium-term. This was confirmed by the results obtained for commercial production (Fig. 10), showing an increase in yield without external P fertilisation in 2021. Fig. 10 also indicates a slight upward trend with the introduction of mycorrhizas, with the highest yield obtained from the MycNoP treatment. It should be noted that 2021 was a year with normal weather conditions, while 2023 was characterised by extreme weather conditions, which affected the commercial yield of potatoes, without yielding clear results.

Fig. 10. Commercial potatoes yield (kg/ha) during the years 2021 and 2023 under the different treatment tested. *Ctrl*, control with a conventional rotation; *PotHP*, conventional rotation with P fertilisation reduced by half, without mycorrhizae; *PotNoP*, conventional rotation without P fertilisation and without mycorrhizae; *MycPotHP*, Introduction of mycorrhizae into potato cycles, with phosphorus (P) fertilisation reduced by half; *MycNoP*, introduction of mycorrhizae into potato cycles, with no P fertilisation applied.

On the other hand, the treatment with mycorrhizal inoculum, without phosphorus (P) fertilisation (MycNoP), enhanced the abundance of Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes. Similarly, the treatments with no P, and particularly those with the introduction of mycorrhizas, resulted in an increased relative abundance of certain nematode groups, such as bacterivores, fungivores, carnivores, and omnivores. This suggests a high level of microbial activity, effective organic matter decomposition, and a well-functioning soil ecosystem. Furthermore, the increase in omnivores reflects a complex and mature ecosystem, characterised by a stable trophic structure and ecological resilience (Ferris et al., 2001). Comparable results were obtained concerning the relative abundance of the Saprotroph–Symbiotroph fungal group, which indicates the availability of organic matter, nutrient recycling, and the enhancement of plant–soil interactions, contributing to ecosystem resilience. Additionally, all alternative treatments led to an approximate 20% increase in the abundance of earthworms (the ecosystem engineers), including both adults and juveniles, with the greatest effect observed in treatments without external P fertilisation and MycPotHP. This is a strong indicator of improved soil structure and fertility (Peltoniemi et al., 2020).

Regarding physicochemical soil properties, the treatments MycNoP and PotHP resulted in an increase in the contents of organic matter (OM), exchangeable magnesium (Mg), bioavailable boron (B), calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), and nitrates, thus enhancing soil fertility.

From an economic point of view, the results of gross margin data for the full crop rotation show that the highest average values were achieved by the treatments where no phosphorus fertiliser was applied (23146 €/ha for MycNoP and 22777 €/ha for PotNoP), despite no significant differences among treatments. However, the observed trends indicate that both treatments are highly effective not only in generating revenue but also in maximising profitability (Table 3). The conventional treatment (Ctrl), despite having a relatively high average gross margin (21,894 €/ha), did not exceed the margins of the non-phosphorus application. This suggests that although conventional practices are reliable, omitting phosphorus fertiliser, especially when combined with mycorrhizal inoculants, can result in greater profitability.

Table 3. Gross margin data for the full crop rotation for the different treatments tested. Data obtained from D6.3. *Ctrl*, control with a conventional rotation; *PotHP*, conventional rotation with P fertilisation reduced by half, without mycorrhizae; *PotNoP*, conventional rotation without P fertilisation and without mycorrhizae; *MycPotHP*, introduction of mycorrhizae into potato cycles, with phosphorus (P) fertilisation reduced by half; *MycNoP*, introduction of mycorrhizae into potato cycles, with no P fertilisation applied.

Treatment	Direct cost (€/ha)	Revenue (€/ha)	Gross margin (€/ha)
Ctrl	13,496.94	31,599.12	21,894.08
MycPotHP	13,337.70	29,039.32	19,186.34
MycNoP	12,777.53	32,074.98	23,146.45
PotHP	12,931.31	26,661.97	16,922.80
PotNoP	12,371.07	31,381.82	22,776.58

In conclusion, considering all the results obtained, phosphorus application is not necessary in the short term, leading to increased gross margins for farmers compared to the conventional treatment. The highest gross margins were achieved with the introduction of mycorrhizas without external P fertilisation (MycNoP treatment), which generally resulted in a well-functioning soil with improved structure and fertility. Although mycorrhizal application did not affect the incidence of common scab, it enhanced profitability and slightly improved soil fertility, as well as the abundance of earthworms and certain microorganism groups. Given the high phosphorus availability in this region, the recommended practices are: **do not apply external P fertilisation**, as it is unnecessary in the medium term, and **introduce mycorrhizas in potato crops**.

Main Benefits of Not Applying External P Fertilisation and Introducing Mycorrhiza in Potato Crops

Based on the results obtained, the implementation of the **MycNoP** treatment (introduction of mycorrhizae into potato cycles, with no P fertilisation applied) will result in the following **benefits**:

- **Increase in soil fertility and structure.**
- **Improvement of soil biodiversity.**
- Enhancement of agricultural system resilience.
- **Increase in economic profitability** for farmers.
- **Decrease in water and soil pollution** due to the reduction of external fertilisation.

4.4.

Potential drawbacks

Not identified.

Case study 5

Lusitanian pedoclimatic region

Exploring the implementation of the Decision Support Systems (DSS) to reduce the use of fungicides in potato and wheat crops and their impact on soil biodiversity

Laura Meno-Fariñas^a, Manuel Conde-Cid^{bc}, Paula Pérez-Rodríguez^{bc}, David Fernández-Calviño^{bc}

^aDepartment of Plant Biology and Soil Sciences, University of Vigo, As Lagoas S/N, Ourense, 32004, Spain

^bSection for Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Department of Plant Biology and Soil Science, Faculty of Sciences, University of Vigo, As Lagoas s/n, Ourense 32004, Spain

^cInstitute of Agroecology and Food (IAA), Universidade de Vigo – Campus Auga, Ourense 32004, Spain

5.1. Study location

Case study 5 (CS5) was conducted in Sandiás (Ourense, north-western Spain), at coordinates 42°05'50.5"N; 7°43'26.7"W (Fig. 11), which formed part of the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region. The area is characterised by an oceanic climate that is generally temperate and humid due to the influence of the Atlantic Ocean. The mean annual temperature is approximately 11.9°C, with annual maximum and minimum temperatures of 26.0°C and -0.8°C, respectively. Average annual precipitation amounts to 766 mm. The soils in this region exhibit very low clay and lime contents, but a high sand content. Accordingly, they are classified as loamy sand and sandy loam.

Fig. 11. CS5 location (to the left) and experimental plot (to the right).

5.2.

Management practices implemented

In the study area, potato is the main crop, typically cultivated in rotation with cereals, particularly wheat. One of the main challenges is the high incidence of fungal diseases affecting potato crops in this region. As a result, large quantities of fungicides are commonly applied using heavy machinery. This practice leads to significant soil compaction and increases the production costs of potatoes due to the reliance on chemical inputs. Moreover, the excessive use of agrochemicals contributes to soil and water pollution, as well as a decline in soil biodiversity.

Taking all this into account, three different treatments were tested during the crop cycles of 2021, 2022, and 2023. In 2021 and 2023, Kennebec variety potatoes were cultivated, while in 2022 the fields were sown with Cabeiro variety wheat. The treatments assessed were as follows:

1. **No fungicide application (Control).**
2. **Routine application**, consisting of fungicide treatments every 7–10 days according to traditional pre-established calendars for potatoes, and a single fungicide application in the case of wheat (**Routine**).
3. **Decision Support System (DSS)-guided application**, in which fungicides were applied based on warnings generated by a late blight control decision support system (**DSS**).

Across all three treatments, identical cultural practices were followed, and the same insecticide and herbicide applications were carried out.

5.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Regarding soil biodiversity, the results indicated that the treatment without fungicide application (Control) led to an enrichment of Firmicutes and Chloroflexi. Similarly, both the no-fungicide treatment (Control) and the Decision Support System (DSS) treatment showed an increase in nematode biodiversity compared to the conventional fungicide application (Routine). However, unexpectedly, the use or absence of fungicides did not appear to have a significant effect on the overall composition of the soil fungal community. Finally, with respect to earthworms, both the DSS and Control treatments resulted in a considerable increase in earthworm abundance and diversity. In conclusion, as expected, both the absence of fungicides (Control treatment) and their reduced use (DSS treatment) generally led to an increase in soil biodiversity.

On the other hand, **regarding crop yield**, the conventional treatment (Routine) resulted in the highest yields for both potato and wheat. **For potatoes** in 2021, the average yield under the Routine treatment was 38,659 kg/ha, whereas the DSS and Control (no fungicide application) treatments yielded 35,342 kg/ha and 25,751 kg/ha, respectively (Fig. 12). In 2023, overall potato production was more variable across replicates and generally lower than in 2021. Nevertheless, the trend among treatments remained consistent with that observed in 2021: the Routine treatment again produced the highest yield (an average of 33,481 kg/ha), followed by the DSS treatment (22,844 kg/ha) and the Control treatment (21,148 kg/ha), respectively (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12. Potato yield under the different treatments tested in 2021 and 2023. *Control*: no fungicide application; *DSS*: Decision Support System-guided fungicide application; *Routine*: routine fungicide application every 7–10 days.

Regarding **wheat yield**, the results indicated that the conventional treatment (Routine) resulted in higher wheat production compared to both the Control (no fungicide application) and DSS (Decision Support System-guided application) treatments. Specifically, under the Routine treatment, wheat yield reached 1,940 kg/ha, while yields under the Control and DSS treatments were similar to each other but considerably lower than that of the conventional treatment. Under the Control treatment, yield was 825 kg/ha, and under the DSS treatment, it was 810 kg/ha.

Fig. 13. Wheat yield under the different treatments tested in 2022. *Control*: no fungicide application; *DSS*: Decision Support System-guided fungicide application; *Routine*: single fungicide application.

Finally, Table 4 presents the gross margin achieved under the different treatments tested. As shown, when considering the full crop rotation, the conventional treatment (Routine, routine fungicide application) incurred the highest direct costs, with an average of €14,544.04/ha, followed by the DSS treatment (Decision Support System-guided fungicide application) with €13,287.03/ha, and the Control treatment (no fungicide application) with €12,528.30/ha. However, despite having the highest production costs, the Routine treatment also yielded significantly higher crop outputs compared to the DSS and Control treatments, resulting in substantially greater revenue (Table 4). Consequently, the Routine treatment achieved the highest average gross margin (€12,603.04/ha), followed by the DSS treatment (€3,690.28/ha), and finally the Control treatment (€4,652.19/ha).

Table 4. Average values of crop revenue, direct production costs and **gross margin**, calculated for each crop cycle and for the full three-year crop rotation. *Control*: no fungicide application; *DSS*: Decision Support System-guided fungicide application; *Routine*: single fungicide application.

Crop	Treatment	Direct cost (€/ha)	Revenue (€/ha)	Gross margin (€/ha)
Potato	Routine	5313.46	9847.49	5715.73
	DSS	5014.36	8872.33	4922.66
	Control	4866.81	6295.51	2184.16
Wheat	Routine	1461.5	485	-918.3
	DSS	1363.61	202.5	-1136.81
	Control	1363.61	206.25	-1132.61
Potato	Routine	7769.08	13905.98	7805.61
	DSS	6909.07	9463.71	3690.28
	Control	6297.88	8837.96	3600.64
Wheat	Routine	14544.04	24238.47	12603.04
	DSS	13287.03	18538.54	7476.13
	Control	12528.3	15339.73	4652.19

In conclusion, considering all the results obtained, it was found that **the absence of fungicide use (Control treatment) or its limited application (DSS treatment) generally led to an increase in soil biodiversity**. This improvement in soil biodiversity observed under treatments with reduced fungicide use may, in the medium to long term, result in enhanced soil fertility and ecosystem services when compared to the conventional system (Routine, routine fungicide application). Additionally, the reduced use of fungicides leads to a decrease in the traffic of heavy machinery, thereby preventing soil compaction. These improvements could, therefore, contribute to the long-term sustainability of agricultural systems by preserving biological activity and reducing pollution associated with agrochemical inputs. However, in the short term, and under the specific climatic conditions of the study period (2021–2023), the findings indicate that the conventional system (Routine) delivered the highest productivity and, consequently, the greatest economic return for farmers. Nonetheless, the enhancements in soil biodiversity associated with the DSS treatment may, over time, lead to increased productivity, potentially making this sustainable approach economically viable. In this regard, longer-term research is required to thoroughly evaluate the economic feasibility of adopting this agricultural practice.

Benefits and Considerations of Implementing a Decision Support System

The implementation of a Decision Support System (DSS) to guide fungicide applications offers notable environmental benefits when compared to conventional approaches, including:

- **Enhanced soil biodiversity**, which may, in the medium to long term, lead to improved soil fertility and key ecosystem services such as nutrient cycling and carbon sequestration.
- **Reduction in the use of synthetic chemical fungicides**, thereby lowering both costs and the risk of soil and water contamination, and reducing impacts on ecological and human health.
- **Reduction in the traffic of heavy machinery in agricultural fields**, preventing soil compaction, which improves soil structure and promotes better root development. This approach also enhances soil biodiversity, reduces fuel consumption, and lowers greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to more sustainable farming practices.

However, from an agronomic perspective, the results obtained during the study period (2021–2023) indicate that this agricultural practice is not currently viable in terms of crop production and economic return when compared with conventional management, as the yields achieved under the DSS approach were significantly lower. Nevertheless, considering the potential long-term benefits of this practice, further extended research is required to more comprehensively assess its agronomic and economic viability.

5.4.

Potential drawbacks

- **Dependence on quality and up-to-date data.** It can be solved with the installation of weather stations
- **Technical complexity.** It can be solved with training lessons and friendly interfaces of applications to smartphones
- **Limited access to infrastructure:** In rural areas with poor connectivity, the system may not be feasible.
- **More research.** Due to a changing weather more years of study are needed to a better understanding and a better adjustment of DSS to the studied area.

Case study 6

Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region

Soil management strategies to improve soil quality while minimizing external input of N and P in potato crops

Lieven Waeyenberge^a and Maarten De Boever^b

^aILVO (Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food), Plant Sciences Unit, Burg. Van Gansberghelaan 96, Merelbeke B-9820, Belgium

^bFlanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), plant Sciences Unit, Merelbeke-Melle, Belgium

6.1.

Study location

Case study 6 was conducted in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region, specifically in the town of Merelbeke–Melle, located in the province of East-Flanders, Belgium (Fig. 14). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots involved in this case study are 50°59'05" N, 3°47'13" E. The climate of this region is characterized as warm and temperate, with a mean annual temperature of 10.5–11°C and mean annual precipitation of 800–900 mm. The soil texture of the field is sandy loam, which typically does not experience water shortages or flooding. However, drought problems can arise during the summer months.

Agricultural activities in East Flanders are influenced by its varied landscapes and soil types and include ornamental horticulture, livestock farming, arable farming, and vegetable cultivation. The main crops grown in the region are sugar beets, grass, cereals, and potatoes, alongside a variety of vegetables cultivated in open fields. Sustainable practices are increasingly being adopted to address critical issues such as nitrate and phosphate leaching into water sources, deficits in soil organic matter, and the overall decline in soil health, including deteriorating biological and structural conditions. However, the high population density in Flanders places additional pressure on biodiversity, further complicating these efforts.

Fig. 14. Location of CS6 in Europe (left) and Belgium (right).

6.2.

Management practices implemented

One of the main agricultural challenges in Flanders is the widespread high levels of phosphorus in agricultural soils. Excessive phosphorus can disrupt microbial activity in the rhizosphere, a crucial process for nutrient cycling, particularly in organic farming systems. Organic growers, who depend on rhizosphere activity for plant nutrition, face a challenge: they must balance the use of organic manure to enhance soil fertility while minimizing the risk of nitrate and phosphate leaching into surface and groundwater.

To mitigate this issue, effective soil management strategies are essential to prevent phosphorus surpluses by carefully regulating external organic matter inputs. In this context, Case study 6 investigated the combined effects of organic fertilization and cover crop management practices to (i) maintain soil quality and (ii) achieve balanced levels of phosphorus.

The field experiment, conducted under an organic farming system, was established on a 0.216-hectare area divided into 24 plots (6 treatments × 4 replicates) using a split-plot design (Fig. 15). Non-inversion tillage practices were implemented, and no herbicides were used. Pest management relied exclusively on products permitted in organic farming. The nitrogen-to-phosphorus (N:P) and carbon-to-phosphorus (C:P) ratios of goat stable manure (farmyard manure) were adjusted by co-composting farmyard manure with 'brown' material (grass clippings from nature reserves). The effects of co-composted farmyard manure, compared to stockpiled farmyard manure, on crop performance and soil quality were assessed over a multiyear field trial involving repeated applications of both fertilization products. The applied doses were calculated using the Flanders' phosphate fertilization standard as limiting factor. A **control treatment** with no base fertilization was also included. Within the same trial, two distinct cover crop management strategies were applied: using cover crop mixtures as green manure (**BAU**) or harvesting them as fodder crops (**AFV**). Variations in these treatments, in terms of both fertilization and cover crop management, are expected to result in differences in carbon, phosphorus, and nitrogen inputs, potentially influencing main crop performance and soil quality.

In summary, the different combinations of fertilization treatments and cover crops managements tested in the present case study were:

- **NB_BAU:** zero-fertilization and cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated.
- **NB_AFV:** zero-fertilization and cover crop mixture mowed and removed.
- **SM_BAU:** farmyard manure and cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated.
- **SM_AFV:** farmyard manure and cover crop mixture mowed and removed.
- **C_BAU:** farmyard manure co-composted with brown material and cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated.
- **C_AFV:** farmyard manure co-composted with brown material and cover crop mixture mowed and removed.

Fig. 15. Experimental lay-out of case-study 6. The experimental area is divided into 4 blocks (red frame) each containing one of six combined treatments (split-plot design): white colored-BAU (control) = conventional farming with cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated, no application of farmyard manure; white colored-AFV = cover crop mowed and removed, no application of farmyard manure; green colored-BAU = conventional farming with cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated, and farmyard manure; green colored-AFV = cover crop mowed and removed, and farmyard manure; yellow colored-BAU = conventional farming with cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated, and farmyard manure composted with 'brown' material (grass clippings from nature reserves); yellow colored-AFV = cover crop mowed and removed, and farmyard manure composted with 'brown' material.

The field experiments were carried out during the crop cycles of 2019 to 2023. In 2019, activities focused on setting up the experiment and standardizing field conditions for each treatment. During the fall of 2019, initial fertilization was applied according to the experimental layout, and the field was sown with a new cover crop mixture comprising 76% summer oats (*Avena sativa*), 12% pea (*Pisum sativum*), 3% Alexandrian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*), and 9% summer vetch (*Vicia sativa*). During subsequent cropping periods, a rotation of cover crops and main crops was maintained, with organic fertilizer application after incorporating the cover crop (Fig. 16): potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum* var. *Vitabella*) in 2020, summer barley (*Hordeum vulgare* var. *Skyway*) in 2022, and savoy cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *sabauda* L.) in 2023. Exceptionally, during the winter of 2021–2022, no cover crop was sown following the main crop because the winter leek crop was maintained throughout the winter season until the next main crop.

Fig. 16. Overview of case-study 6 concerning management practices, crop cycle and data gathering.

6.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Based on the results from Case study 6, the best management practice appears to be the use of farmyard manure combined with cover crops incorporated into the soil (SM_BAU), as this practice showed several advantages.

Regarding soil fertility and, consequently, crop yields, farmyard manure (SM) led to significantly higher yields (Fig. 17), especially for nitrogen-intensive crops like potatoes and savoy cabbage, compared to co-composted farmyard manure (C) or no fertilization at all (NB). Soil chemical analyses revealed that the use of farmyard manure (SM) contributed to a balanced soil pH, electrical conductivity, and the availability of important nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and magnesium. These elements are critical for maintaining soil fertility and ensuring optimal nutrient cycling. This suggests that farmyard manure enhances soil fertility, nutrient availability, and microbial activity, ultimately improving crop performance. Farmyard manure application also improved levels of organic carbon content, a key indicator of soil health and organic matter content. Organic matter is essential for maintaining soil structure, moisture retention, and nutrient supply, which benefits long-term crop production.

Fig. 17. Yield of potato depending on the fertilizer. Control (NB), Co-composted FYM = farmyard manure co-composted with brown material (C), FYM = farmyard manure (SM).

Fig. 18. Yield of potato depending on the cover crop management. BAU (control) = conventional farming with cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated; AFV = cover crop mowed and removed.

When cover crops were incorporated into the soil (BAU) rather than removed after mowing (AFV), there was also a noticeable increase in crop yields (Fig. 18). This suggests that the nutrients from the decomposed cover crops added to the soil helped improve the growth environment for the main crops.

Regarding biodiversity, treatments showed no significant differentiation in microbial diversity. However, a trend emerged, suggesting greater abundances when farmyard manure (SM) was applied compared to co-composted material (C) or no fertilizer (NB), regardless of cover crop management. The bacterial communities were dominated by beneficial groups like Proteobacteria and Actinobacteria (Fig. 19). These microbes are crucial for a productive, sustainable farming system, especially under organic practices. They promote nutrient cycling and efficient organic matter decomposition, which support plant growth and soil ecosystem health. The results were confirmed by a trend showing greater prokaryotic gene abundance in treatments where farmyard manure was used, suggesting more active processes in carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles. This further supports the idea that farmyard manure improves nutrient availability, contributing to overall long-term soil health and crop growth.

The presence of Acidobacteria (Fig. 19), a group of microbes that thrive in suboptimal conditions, suggested that farmyard manure improved the soil's ability to maintain microbial activity even under environmental stress. This indicates the soil's resilience, which is a key characteristic of healthy, sustainable agricultural systems.

The use of farmyard manure, particularly when combined with cover crop incorporation (SM_BAU), led to improved fungal community composition, with a decrease in pathotrophic fungi (disease-causing fungi) and an increase in beneficial saprotrophic fungi, which play a role in decomposing organic matter and supporting plant health.

Fig. 19. Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant prokaryotic phyla in case study 6. 1 = control = conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, no application of farmyard manure (NB_BAU); 2 = cover crop mowed and removed, no application of farmyard manure (NB_AFV); 3 = cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, with farmyard manure (SM_BAU); 4 = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material (C_AFV); 5 = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure (SM_AFV); 6 = cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated with farmyard manure composted with 'brown' material (C_BAU).

An impact of the different treatments on the diversity of soil nematode communities could not be clearly demonstrated. It is more likely that an external factor, such as climatic conditions, played a significant role in influencing changes to the nematode community.

While no significant effect of farm management treatments on earthworm populations was observed, earthworm numbers increased by the end of the experiment across all management combinations, with organic fertilizer application further boosting populations. Organic fertilization (e.g., farmyard manure) is known to promote earthworm activity, which, in turn, improves soil structure, moisture retention, and organic matter decomposition—critical factors for sustainable soil management.

Finally, regarding economic viability, it was found that the treatment with farmyard manure and cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated (SM_BAU) presented the highest gross margin (35,563.27 €/ha), followed by the treatment with farmyard manure and cover crop mixture mowed and removed (SM_AFV), with a gross margin of 29,113.18 €/ha, farmyard manure co-composted with brown material and cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated (C_BAU), with a gross margin of 27,204.73 €/ha, farmyard manure co-composted with brown material and cover crop mixture mowed and removed (C_AFV), with a gross margin of 23,169.54 €/ha, zero-fertilization and cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated (NB_BAU), with a gross margin of 22,210.57 €/ha, and finally, zero-fertilization and cover crop mixture mowed and removed (NB_AFV), with a gross margin of 20,089.25 €/ha. As shown, the treatments with no fertilization (NB) resulted in the lowest economic benefits. Moreover, it is evident that, in all cases, the incorporation of cover crops led to higher economic benefits compared to their removal.

Main Benefits of the Incorporation of Cover Crops and of the Use of Farmyard Manure (SM_BAU)

- It enhances soil health and crop yields, attributes to balanced soil pH and optimal nutrient availability.
- It tends to improve soil microbial activity potentially leading to reduced nitrogen leakage and balanced phosphor levels.
- It improves microbial resilience.
- It influences fungal community composition, increasing beneficial saprotrophic fungi while decreasing pathotrophic fungi.
- It further boosts earthworm populations.
- It generates higher economic benefits.

6.4.

Potential drawbacks

A specific farmyard manure (goat manure) was used. This potentially affects fungal diversity overruling other agricultural management treatments. It is known that a decrease in overall fungal diversity due to farmyard manure can be expected, since the fungal community may have changed more towards “manure specific” taxa (Zhang et al., 2022). Whether this is a positive or negative issue depends on the goals.

Climatological factors can overrule the mentioned positive impacts of the investigated farming management practices. Although the quality of the potatoes (based on starch content) could be considered as normal, the potato yield (2020) was generally low for all treatments examined. Most likely, the exceptionally dry year and no irrigation applied was the most important factor as potato tubers needs plenty of water to develop.

Case study 7

Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region

Cover crop mixtures: a promotor of soil biodiversity in potato crops?

Jasper Vanbesien^a and Lieven Waeyenberge^b

^aWeed Science Unit, Department of Plants and Crops, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Gent, Belgium

^bILVO (Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food), Plant Sciences Unit, Burg. Van Gansberghelaan 96, Merelbeke B-9820, Belgium

7.1.

Study location

Case study 7 was conducted in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region, specifically in the province of West-Flanders in the northwest of Belgium (Fig. 20). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots involved in this case study are 50°54'23.1" N, 3°07'41.9" E. The climate of this region is characterised as warm and temperate, with a mean annual temperature of 10.5°C and an average annual precipitation of 836 mm. The soil texture of the field is sandy loam, which typically does not experience water shortages or flooding. However, drought problems can arise during the summer months.

Fig. 20. Location of CS7 in Europe (left) and Belgium (right).

West-Flanders has a diverse and highly productive agricultural sector as a result of its fertile soils, temperate climate, and proximity to major European markets. The main agricultural activities in West-Flanders include horticulture, livestock farming, arable farming, and the agri-food processing sector. The principal crops grown in the region are sugar beet, grass, cereals, and potatoes, alongside a variety of vegetables cultivated in open fields, such as carrots, cabbages, onions, celery, and leek. The region makes a significant contribution to Flanders' agricultural export strength, with an emphasis on processed potato products, dairy, meat, and horticultural produce.

Sustainable practices are increasingly being adopted to address the impacts of climate change, economic pressure, and agricultural regulations concerning nitrate and phosphate leaching, CO₂ emissions, deficits in soil organic matter, and the overall decline in soil health, including deterioration of biological and structural conditions. These challenges and responses underscore the complex landscape in which farmers in West-Flanders operate, balancing environmental responsibilities with economic sustainability.

7.2.

Management practices implemented

The western region of Belgium is a key area for potato and seed potato cultivation. Regional stakeholder meetings have highlighted that addressing soil-related issues is a high priority for improving potato production. The most pressing concerns identified include increasing levels of soil organic matter (SOM), enhancing soil structure, and improving soil fertility. Among the management techniques discussed, the addition of organic matter and/or manure, as well as the use of cover crops, were ranked as the most effective solutions.

In organic agriculture, maintaining a rich and complex biodiversity within the soil is crucial. Soil biology must be capable of decomposing diverse organic materials to supply crops with adequate nutrients in a timely manner. Furthermore, soil microorganisms play a vital role in controlling soilborne diseases. Incorporating species-rich cover crop mixtures can enhance soil biology, elevating its functionality to a higher level.

The main objective of case study 7 was to test the impact of species-rich cover crop mixtures in organic agriculture on soil biological diversity, as well as on the yield and quality of primary crops. The study aimed to provide practical insights for farmers to optimize the design of their cover crop mixtures. Additionally, the study sought to address key questions, such as whether species-diverse mixtures can combine multiple soil-beneficial functions, including nitrogen capture, and whether the inclusion of leguminous species in the mix contributes additional nitrogen to subsequent primary crops. Advisors often recommend organic farmers to use species-diverse cover crop mixtures to stimulate soil diversity. However, little is known about the actual impact of these mixtures on soil diversity, either in the short or longer term.

The experimental design involved testing four different cover crop mixtures (Fig. 21). To enhance diversification, the number of species in each mixture was increased, with particular emphasis on the inclusion of leguminous species. Leguminous species add significant value as green manure through their symbiotic relationship with nitrogen-fixing bacteria, which capture nitrogen (N) from the atmosphere. The cover crops used were primarily frost-sensitive, typically dying off almost entirely by late winter. This characteristic facilitated easy mechanical destruction, enabling efficient soil preparation for the subsequent main crop.

Fig. 21. Diversity of the cover crop mixtures applied in CS7. 1 = Phacelia and Black oat, a "business as usual" mix; 2 = Phacelia and Egyptian clover, a simple leguminous/non leguminous mix; 3 = 5-species mix including Phacelia, Black oat, Egyptian clover, Winter vetch and Fodder radish, a medium diverse mix; 4 = 12-species mix including Phacelia, Black oat, Egyptian clover, Spring vetch, Fodder radish, Forage radish (Tillage radish), Pea, Lupin, Serradella, Niger, Alsike clover and Flax, a highly diverse mix.

It was decided to conduct the trial on one of the testing fields of Inagro's experimental farm for organic production (12 ha of fields). This farm is unique in Flanders and plays a pivotal role in advancing organic farming in the region. Its integration within the broader structure of Inagro facilitates a robust exchange of techniques and knowledge between organic and conventional farming methods. Since 2016, Controlled Traffic Farming (CTF) has been implemented on the Inagro organic farm. Thus, during the growing season, all field operations were carried out using a specially adapted tractor equipped with RTK-GPS technology (Fig. 22). This cultivation system preserves the 3-meter-wide planting beds from structural damage. Complementary to the introduction of CTF in 2016, ploughing was discontinued, instead soil and cover crops were managed according to reduced-till methods thereafter. In early spring, cover crop remains were flail mowed, and then only superficially worked in with a precision cultivator (till a depth of 3–5 cm). The preparation of the soil for sowing/planting the main crop consisted only of subsoiling (0–30 cm) and power harrowing (0–10 cm). After the main crop harvest, these same tools were again used to prepare the seedbed for the new cover crops. Fertilisation usually involved farmyard manure and/or commercial organic fertilizer pellets. Fertiliser type and application dose were determined based on soil analysis and an estimation of nitrogen mineralisation from soil organic matter (SOM) and crop residues. In the first season 30 tons/ha cattle farmyard manure (227 kg Ntot/ha) and 0,39 tons/ha fertilizer pellets (50 kg Ntot/ha) were applied. In the second season no fertilizer was used. In the third season 30 tons/ha cattle farmyard manure (239 kg Ntot/ha) was applied.

Fig. 22. John Deere tractor with 3 m wide wheel axle.

Case study 7 involved a multi-year trial designed to align with the fixed six-year crop rotation of the aforementioned farm (Fig. 23). This rotation includes both vegetable and arable crops ending with potatoes. Main crops were:

2021	Broccoli	Season 1
2022	Red beet	Season 2
2023	Potato	Season 3

Over three consecutive years (2020, 2021, and 2022), identical cover crop mixtures were sown post-harvest in the same locations and at consistent doses. The field experimental area was 0,162 ha divided according to a randomized block design into 16 plots (4 treatments x 4 replicates; Fig. 24).

Fig. 23. Overview of case-study 7 concerning management practices, crop cycle and data gathering.

The different treatments tested consisted of four distinct cover crop mixtures (Fig. 24):

1. Phacelia + black oat (**BAU**);
2. Phacelia + Egyptian clover (**Mix 1**).
3. A five-species mixture (Phacelia, black oat, Egyptian clover, winter vetch, and fodder radish) (**Mix 2**).
4. A twelve-species mixture (Phacelia, black oat, Egyptian clover, spring vetch, fodder radish, forage radish, pea, lupin, serradella, niger, alsike clover, and flax) (**Mix 3**).

Fig. 24. Experimental lay-out of case-study 7. The experimental area is divided into 18 plots of which 16 are occupied for the experiment: 1-4.01 = BAU ('business-as -usual') = Phacelia and Black oat; 1-4.02 = a simple leguminous/non leguminous mix = Phacelia and Egyptian clover cover crop; 1-4.03 = 5-species mix including Phacelia, Black oat, Egyptian clover, Winter vetch and Fodder radish = a medium diverse mix; 1-4.04 = 12-species mix including Phacelia, Black oat, Egyptian clover, Spring vetch, Fodder radish, Forage radish (Tillage radish), Pea, Lupin, Serradella, Niger, Alsike clover and Flax = a highly diverse mix.

7.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Based on the results from Case study 7, **the 5-species cover crop mixture (Mix 2)** emerged as the best overall agricultural practice in terms of balancing yield and biodiversity. However, many of the results were not statistically significant or entirely conclusive and further research is needed.

In the first place, regarding cover crop yield and biomass stability, the 5-species (Mix 2) and 12-species (Mix 3) mixtures consistently produced the highest and most stable aboveground biomass yields (Fig. 25).

Fig. 25. Cover crop growth during the 3 seasons (2021–2023).

Since biomass is strongly linked to nitrogen availability—a key nutrient for crops—the high biomass from these mixtures increased nitrogen availability to subsequent crops (0–90 cm soil layer), especially during the first two years (Fig. 26). Significant differences were only measured in August 2021, and not at other timepoints. It appears that nitrogen was partially released from the biomass through mineralisation after its destruction (via frost and flail mowing) and subsequent incorporation into the soil. The lowest availability was observed with the Phacelia/ Egyptian clover mixture (Mix 1) despite the (partial) presence of a legume.

Fig. 26. The evolution of plant-available nitrate nitrogen in the 0–90 cm soil layer (kg/ha) over the trial years as a function of the choice of cover crop mixture.

In the second place, regarding potato crop yield, although the effects on final marketable yield of potato were not statistically significant, trends were generally positive for the more complex mixtures, particularly the 5-species mixture (Mix 2) (Fig. 27). Internal cavities and brown-black discolourations were seen in the non-marketable potatoes, suspected to have a physiological cause: limited availability of nutrients during a growth spurt after a period of dry weather for of a sensitive potato cultivar *Nirvana*. Additionally, but no less important, there was no risk of higher nitrate nitrogen residues after main crop harvest (in autumn) prone to leaching out in winter due to the (partial) presence of leguminous plants in the mixes, compared to the standard mix without leguminous plants. The difference in function of cover crop choice was negligible.

Fig. 27. Potato crop yield (2023).

In third place, regarding microbial activity, the results highlighted the limited impact of the treatments on microbial diversity and overall abundance. However, specific gene abundances—particularly *nirK* (Nitrite Reductase gene) and *ureC* (Urease Alpha Subunit gene)—were influenced by the cover crop mixtures.

NirK increased in the 5-species mixture (Mix 2). This gene is linked to denitrification, a key part of the nitrogen cycle. An increase in *nirK* suggests improved nitrogen turnover, with more efficient cycling of excess nitrate. This helps reduce nitrogen leaching into groundwater and can contribute to higher crop yields, as the results showed a positive correlation with yield.

In contrast, the 12-species mixture (Mix 3) led to reduced *ureC* gene activity. *UreC* encodes for urease, an enzyme that hydrolyzes urea into ammonia (NH_3) and carbon dioxide (CO_2). A decrease in *ureC* activity suggests lower ammonia emissions and better nitrogen retention in the soil in less volatile forms, such as ammonium (NH_4^+) or nitrate (NO_3^-).

An increase in *nirK* (as seen with the 5-species mixture, Mix 2) and a decrease in *ureC* (as seen with the 12-species mixture, Mix 3) can each be interpreted as positive, depending on the context. However, these changes may also indicate competitive or inhibitory effects among species in the more complex mixtures. The increase of a functional and useful gene makes the 5-species mixture more balanced and beneficial from a microbial perspective. It underscores the importance of thoughtful design when selecting cover crop mixtures to maximize their benefits for soil microbial health and nutrient cycling.

In fourth place, there were no indications that the different cover crop mixtures influenced fungal, nematode and earthworm diversity or community composition. All treatments, including the control, for instance resulted in an increase in nematode biodiversity, indicating a more mature and stable nematode community. However, no clear link was established between nematode diversity, soil parameters, and yield, suggesting that external factors influenced biodiversity more than the treatments themselves.

Finally, regarding economic viability, considering the last year (2023), in which potatoes were cultivated, it was found that the treatments Mix 2 (five-species cover crop mixture) and Mix 3 (twelve-species cover crop mixture) resulted in gross margins similar to those obtained for the BAU (Business as Usual) treatment. In this sense, for the BAU treatment, a gross margin of 4756.54 €/ha was obtained, while for the Mix 2 and Mix 3 treatments, the gross margins obtained were 4533.39 and 4425.39 €/ha, respectively. In contrast, Mix 1 resulted in a considerably lower gross margin, specifically 3288.46 €/ha.

Many of the observed effects were not statistically significant, and external factors such as weather and soil conditions most probably played a major role in shaping outcomes. Therefore, while the 5-species mixture shows promising potential, caution is warranted in drawing definitive conclusions, and further research is needed to validate these results across longer timeframes and broader conditions.

Main Benefits of Applying a Five-Species Cover Crop Mixture (Mix 2)

Based on the findings from case study 7, the five-species cover crop mixture (**Mix 2**) treatment appears to be the best overall agricultural practice. In this sense, this agricultural practice presents the following benefits:

- High and stable aboveground cover crop biomass production.
- Increased nitrogen availability to subsequent crops, thus improving soil fertility.
- Increased potato crop marketable yield.
- Improved biodiversity, particularly with respect to genes related to denitrification, which improves nitrogen turnover, with more efficient cycling of excess nitrate.
- Maintenance of economic profitability.

7.4.

Potential drawbacks

Maintaining cover crop diversity throughout the growing period is challenging. The results demonstrated that above-ground biomass production by cover crop mixtures is highly variable, with species ratios fluctuating significantly from year to year (Fig. 25). In more complex mixtures, diversity often declines as certain plant species fail to thrive or grow unevenly due to varying climatic and environmental conditions. Additionally, factors such as sowing time, seed quality, and soil parameters likely influenced these variations. On the other hand, species-diverse mixes are more flexible to use for a lot of different environmental conditions compared to species-poor cover crops.

Caution is warranted regarding plant pests and diseases. Complex mixtures may include plant species from the same family as the main crop, which could serve as hosts for pests and increase their impact on the subsequent main crop. For instance, in 2021, a small increase in rhizoctonia incidence in broccoli was observed, likely due to the presence of radishes (from the cabbage family) in the 5-species cover crop mixture.

Case study 8

Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region

Intensive versus extensive versus organic vegetable farming

Renik Van den Eynde^a, Sander Fleerackers^a, Lieven Waeyenberge^b

^aResearch Station for Vegetable Production, Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium

^bILVO (Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food), Plant Sciences Unit, Burg. Van Gansberghelaan 96, Merelbeke B-9820, Belgium

8.1.

Study location

Case study 8 (CS8) was conducted in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region, specifically in the town of Sint-Katelijne-Waver in the province of Antwerp, Belgium (Fig. 28). It was carried out on two separate fields located within 1 km of each other, one non-organic (GPS coordinates: 51°04'33" N, 4°31'46" E) and one organically certified field (GPS coordinates: 51°04'33" N, 4°32'19" E). The climate of this region is warm and temperate, with a mean annual temperature of 11.5°C and mean annual precipitation of 716 mm. The soil texture of the field is sandy loam, with a superficial clay layer. Such soil types have relatively less likelihood of water shortage, but the clay layer increases the risk of flooding.

Fig. 28. CS8 location in Europe (to the left) and Belgium (to the right).

In Antwerp, Belgium, agriculture is not the dominant economic activity due to the region's high urbanisation and industrialisation, especially around the port of Antwerp. However, in the more rural and southern parts of the province, agriculture still plays a role. The main agricultural activities include arable farming, livestock farming, and especially horticulture with vegetable cultivation both in open fields and greenhouses. Common vegetables include leeks, carrots, cabbages, lettuce, tomatoes and peppers.

In Belgium, approximately 45% of outdoor vegetable production occurs under intensive farming systems, while the remainder is cultivated within crop rotations that include arable crops, representing more extensive farming practices. Intensive vegetable production is characterised by limited crop rotation, intensive tillage, and unilateral fertilisation. While this approach maximises short-term productivity, it has significant drawbacks for

soil quality and overall sustainability. It also fosters an environment conducive to pests and diseases, which can ultimately reduce crop yield and quality. By contrast, extensive farming practices—including broader crop rotations, reduced tillage, and increased organic matter input—are known to have a positive influence on soil biodiversity and resilience.

8.2.

Management practices implemented

The aim of case study 8 was to explore ways to transition from intensive to more extensive farming practices. Specifically, the study investigated how techniques such as non-inverting tillage, the application of organic matter, and increased use of cover crops can be feasibly implemented. These techniques are already recognised for their beneficial effects on soil health, yet their practical adoption requires careful consideration and collaboration with growers. Through this approach, the study sought to provide actionable recommendations to farmers, demonstrating how these changes can improve soil life and biodiversity while addressing concerns about feasibility and potential impacts on yield. Organic vegetable farming systems are inherently more extensive due to their broad crop rotations, higher input of organic matter, and reduced reliance on synthetic crop protection agents. On average, these practices result in richer soil biodiversity. However, even within organic farming, there is variation between farms—some already implement extensive management practices, while others remain uncertain about their viability. This study aimed to identify how organic farming techniques can further extensify their systems and determine whether similar effects on soil life can be achieved in conventional farming systems through the adoption of extensive practices.

Case study 8 was set-up to provide a comprehensive comparison of farming approaches, contrasting conventional farming with organic farming, and intensive farming (characterized by conventional tillage and no cover crops) with extensive farming (which incorporates reduced tillage, cover crops, and compost applications) (Fig. 29). One of the primary objectives was to demonstrate to growers that investing in healthy soil—despite potentially slower immediate returns such as lower yields—can lead to long-term benefits in crop health and productivity. By building confidence in the tangible advantages of these practices, this study sought to encourage broader adoption of sustainable farming techniques.

Fig. 29. Visual representation of crop management practices and main objectives in Case study 8.

To facilitate the comparison of farming systems, two fields were used for this trial (2 x 0.1 ha). The first field had been conventionally cultivated for several years, following an intensive vegetable rotation. The second field, in contrast, had recently been converted to organic farming. During the two-year conversion period, the organic field was sown with a grass-clover mixture to improve soil quality and fertility. Both fields were further divided into two parts, each managed with a different cultivation system. This setup resulted in four distinct treatments, each of them consisting of four (semi-) replications of 120 m². (Fig. 30):

1. **Organic and intensive (A):** organic fields were fertilised using organic fertiliser such as cattle slurry, farmyard manure (cattle), and NK (11-3) organic fertiliser. Inverting tillage (spading) was utilised for soil management.
2. **Organic and extensive (B):** similar to A, organic fertiliser was the primary source of soil nutrients in this treatment together with green waste compost. However, reduced tillage methods (fixed tooth cultivator + shallow rotary tiller) were implemented, and cover crops were used.
3. **Conventional and intensive (control) (C):** the intensively cultivated plots in this treatment were characterised by inverting tillage and the absence of cover crops in the crop rotation. Mineral fertilisers were used for soil nutrient supplementation.
4. **Conventional and extensive (D):** in the conventional extensive treatment, compost was used along with chemical fertilizer for soil enrichment. Reduced tillage practices were employed in this approach and cover crops were used.

Fig. 30. Experimental lay-out of case-study 8. The experimental area was organised on 2 separate fields (A+B and C+D) each divided into 2 x 4 plots. A = organic intensive, B = organic extensive, C = conventional intensive, D = conventional extensive.

The trial was maintained during four growing seasons. The cropping cycle was as follows (*: only in extensive treatments):

- **Season 1 (2020–2021):** Autumn Leek (var Oslo) *Allium porrum* planting end of June, harvest end of October/November. *Cover crop spring 2021 *Phacelia tanacetifolia* + Crimson clover *Trifolium incarnatum*.
- **Season 2 (2021–2022):** Celery (var Tango) *Apium graveolens* planting end of June, harvest end of September. *Cover crop autumn 2021 Ryegrass mixture.
- **Season 3 (2022–2023):** Cauliflower (different varieties) *Brassica oleracea* var *botrytis* planting in April and harvest in June, secondary crop Cauliflower planting in July and harvest in October. *Cover crop 2022 between cultures *Phacelia tanacetifolia*.
- **Season 4 (2023–2024):** Roman lettuce (var Picador) *Lactuca sativa* var *longifolia* planting in June and harvest in July, secondary crop Roman lettuce planting in July and harvest in September.

8.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Based on the results from case study 8, the best agricultural practice appears to be extensive farming.

In the first place, regarding yield and quality, across multiple crop types, extensive treatments delivered better yields (e.g. Fig. 31) and higher product quality. This outcome was consistent regardless of whether the farming approach was conventional or organic. The improved yield performance is closely linked to healthier soil conditions in extensive systems—such as balanced pH, higher nitrogen content, and stronger microbial activity—all of which are essential for supporting plant growth.

In the second place, regarding soil health and microbial activity, extensive farming systems also contributed significantly to better soil health and ecological balance. Visual observations from the study revealed that soils managed extensively had faster water infiltration and greater load-bearing capacity—critical traits for timely machinery access after rainfall and overall field operability. These features indicate a more stable and resilient soil structure, which aligns with the higher earthworm densities recorded in extensive plots.

In third place, regarding soil biodiversity, extensive systems supported a richer and more functional soil microbial community. They harbored higher abundances of saprotrophic fungi, which play a vital role in organic matter decomposition and nutrient release, as well as arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) that form symbiotic relationships with plant roots, improving nutrient uptake—especially phosphorus and nitrogen—while enhancing soil structure and plant health.

Fig. 31. Mean (net) production of celery in 2021 (tons /ha) and mean infestation of *Septoria apiicola* leaf spot on celery in 2021 (score 1 to 9, the lower the score the higher the infestation).

Beneficial bacterial phyla were more abundant in extensive systems, accompanied by increased activity of key nutrient cycling genes, such as *amoA* and *nirK*, although their expression varied between farming systems. Conventional extensive farming showed elevated activity of both genes: *amoA* enhances nitrification, making nitrogen more readily available to plants, while *nirK* is associated with denitrification, which can lead to nitrogen leakage in water reservoirs and loss as gases in the atmosphere. This combination may boost short-term soil fertility, but it also increases the risk of nitrogen shortage on the long-term. In contrast, organic systems exhibited lower activity of these genes, suggesting more stable nitrogen dynamics that support long-term fertility with a reduced risk of nitrogen loss.

Regarding earthworms, particularly endogenic and anecic types, are important for soil aeration, nutrient cycling, and organic matter decomposition, all of which were more prevalent in extensive systems (Fig. 32). Nematode community composition also showed greater evenness and balance in extensive systems, reflecting a maturing and more stable soil ecosystem.

Fig. 32. Mean number of earthworms per 10 dm³ of the different treatments after the cropping season in 2020, 2021 and 2023.

Finally, regarding economic viability, the analysis revealed that organic farming systems achieved significantly higher gross margins compared to conventional production systems. While the costs associated with organic farming are generally higher, these are more than compensated for the increased revenues, resulting in a more favourable economic outcome. Among the organic systems, the extensive model yielded the highest gross margin (179,965.30 €/ha), making it economically more attractive than the intensive organic system, which reported a gross margin of 156,570.90 €/ha.

In contrast, for conventional vegetable production, the economic difference between extensive (46,408.85 €/ha) and intensive (50,038.85 €/ha) systems was less pronounced and appeared to depend largely on the type of crop cultivated.

Benefits of Implementing Extensive Agricultural Systems

Based on the results obtained, the implementation of extensive agricultural systems appears to offer the following benefits:

- Increase in crop yield and enhanced product quality.
- Increase in nitrogen content and more balanced pH, thus leading to an improvement in soil fertility.
- Improved soil structure.
- Richer and more functional soil microbial community, enhancing both soil fertility and structure, as well as nutrient uptake by plants.
- In organic farming systems, extensive practices yield the greatest economic benefit.

8.4.

Potential drawbacks

To implement these measures, farmers need adapted machinery for soil tillage. However, in this case study, machinery equipment is chosen that is generally part of an average intensive vegetable farm. In this way, no new investments should be done to implement the reduced soil tillage.

The system of leasing farmland of landowners is widely used in Flanders, to widen the crop rotation on the farmland when managed by specialised farms. This means that more farmers are cultivating the soil. To achieve the longterm effects of the management practices, every farmer should invest in the soil quality in order to not nullify the efforts of implementing an extensive management.

Case study 9

Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region

Improving agro-ecological crop production by application of different sources of green manure

Lieven Waeyenberge^a and Lieven Bauwens^b

^aILVO (Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food), Plant Sciences Unit, Burg. Van Gansberghelaan 96, Merelbeke B-9820, Belgium

^bPomona VZW, Dillaartwijk 81 9100 Sint-Niklaas, Belgium

9.1.

Study location

Case study 9 was conducted in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region, specifically in the town of Beveren in the province of East-Flanders, Belgium (Fig. 33). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots involved in this case study are 51°16′03.5″ N, 4°11′03.6″. The climate of this region is warm and temperate, with a mean annual temperature of 10.5–11°C and mean annual precipitation of 800–900 mm. The soil type of the field is classified as ‘Pep’ (texture class light sandy loam, drainage class wet and no soil profile development). Such soil types are typically wet and suffer from flooding during the winter, but they dry late during the spring and remain moist during the summer.

Fig. 33. Location of CS9 in Europe (left) and Belgium (right).

Agricultural activities in East Flanders are influenced by its varied landscapes and soil types and include ornamental horticulture, livestock farming, arable farming, and vegetable cultivation. The main crops grown in the region are sugar beets, grass, cereals, and potatoes, alongside a variety of vegetables cultivated in open fields.

Sustainable practices, particularly those associated with organic farming, are continually evolving due to advancements in research, technology, and local initiatives. In Belgium, the total area dedicated to organic farming remains limited, and the biodiversity value is notably low. This situation presents significant challenges in protecting biodiversity and ensuring the long-term survival of ecosystems and the essential services they provide.

Beyond further reducing the use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers, it is crucial to diversify production methods even more while actively involving farmers in landscape management. However, many farmers are reluctant to adopt biodiversity-supporting management practices, such as agro-ecological farming. This hesitation stems from the perception that these practices are unproductive, unprofitable, and heavily reliant on substantial subsidies, despite growing awareness of their importance. Nevertheless, some studies, such as van der Ploeg (2019), have demonstrated the potential of agro-ecological farming to be economically sustainable. Unfortunately, research of this kind is very limited and has yet to definitively prove that, over the long term, agro-ecological farming can foster economic resilience, reduce input costs, improve soil health, and enhance biodiversity. These characteristics make this way of farming a promising approach for sustainable agriculture. To gain broader acceptance from farmers and other stakeholders, further research is essential.

9.2.

Management practices implemented

Case study 9, organized by Pomona—a consumer-driven cooperative agroforestry farm—served as an example of sustainable agricultural management in practice. In this context, the field experiment followed an agro-ecological approach. The farming system included no-till or reduced tillage without conversion, combined with the application of green organic matter as fertilizer. Main crops were sown or planted manually, and no herbicides, pesticides, or other chemicals were used. A cover crop was cultivated between the main crops and incorporated into the soil after destruction.

Pomona's approach strives to achieve a perfect balance between a fully developed ecosystem and profitable crop production, while meeting consumer needs. In this regard, it was decided as the primary objective of the case study to test various sources of locally produced organic fertilizers to increase soil organic matter content, improve soil structure, and enhance plant health and development. In particular, farmyard manure, compost and fermented organic waste (such as silage grass clover) were evaluated. The experimental area covers approximately 1.2 hectares. Two rows, each measuring 8 meters by 300 meters, are designated for the case study. Each row is subdivided into two plots, resulting in a total of four plots, one for each planned treatment. One plot did not receive any organic fertilizer (**BAU**), while the remaining three plots received different types of green manure: (i) farmyard manure (cattle manure) (**FYM**), (ii) compost (**COM**), and (iii) fermented organic material (grass silage) (**FOM**). The first two types of green manure were produced locally, whereas the fermented grass was produced on the farm. In total, there are 16 plots (4 treatments x 4 replicates).

Fig. 34. Overview of case-study 9 concerning management practices, crop cycle and data gathering.

The field experiments (Fig. 34) were conducted during the crop cycles from 2020 to 2023. The 2020–2021 cropping period was used solely to set up the experiment and homogenize the field conditions. *Triticum spelta* was grown across the entire field trial area (1.2 hectares), and no green manure or other fertilization methods were applied. During the 2021–2022 cropping period, *Triticum spelta* was again grown on the entire field trial area following the incorporation of a cover crop (*Raphanus sativus*). Before sowing the cover crop, fertilization was applied according to the aforementioned treatments. In the 2022–2023 cropping period, the field trial management mirrored the previous cropping cycle. However, instead of *Raphanus sativus* and *Triticum spelta*, *Phacelia* and *Solanum tuberosum* were cultivated. The latter consisted of a mixture of two varieties: *S. tuberosum* cv. Alouette and Cammeo (size 28–35 mm).

9.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

The findings from case study 9 suggest that no single organic fertilization strategy can be universally recommended, as no single organic fertilizer treatment emerged as universally superior across all ecological and agricultural indicators. However, when considering crop productivity, indicators of soil health, and economic performance, compost (COM) and fermented grass silage (FOM) emerged as the most promising options for potato production. On the other hand, regarding spelt, from a perspective of productive and economic performance, farmyard manure (FYM) seems to be the best option. However, this treatment raised certain ecological concerns.

In the first place, regarding crop yield, in comparison to the control treatment (BAU, without organic fertilization), yields of *Solanum tuberosum* (Fig. 35) were higher when compost (COM) or fermented silage grass (FOM) was applied, while farmyard manure (FYM) not only failed to produce comparable results but was also associated with a greater loss of marketable potatoes. This may be attributed to factors such as nutrient imbalances or an increased risk of disease or pest pressure often linked with improperly managed manure. Regarding *Triticum spelta*, yields showed differing results across the treatments compared to potato (Fig. 36). This suggests that green manure applications did not offer a similar agronomic advantage for this particular crop under the conditions of the study. Nonetheless, farmyard manure (FYM) did not negatively impact the grain quality, indicating it may still have a role in systems where maintaining organic matter or nutrient cycling is a priority.

Fig. 35. Yield (kg/ha) of potato in 2023 depending on the fertilizer. BAU = no fertilizer, COM = compost, FYM = farmyard manure, FOM = silage grass.

Fig. 36. Yield (kg/ha) of *Triticum spelta* in 2021 (set-up of the experiment) and 2022 depending on the fertilizer. BAU = no fertilizer, COM = compost, FYM = farmyard manure, FOM = silage grass.

In the second place, from a soil biology perspective, the study did not reveal major differences in microbial abundance or diversity among the treatments. Although various soil factors—such as pH, moisture, electrical conductivity, and trace metal availability—did influence microbial and fungal communities, these effects could not be directly linked to the type of organic fertilizer used. Similarly, while fungal guilds showed some treatment-specific associations, overall fungal diversity and community composition were not significantly altered.

When it comes to soil fauna, all treatments resulted in a general increase in nematode abundance and diversity, reflecting a potential improvement in soil health. However, these changes appeared to be more strongly influenced by the use of cover crops than by the fertilization treatments themselves. Fermented grass silage (FOM) stood out slightly among the options, as it was the only treatment that led to a clear—albeit statistically non-significant—increase in earthworm numbers from the beginning to the end of the experiment (Fig. 37). This suggests that fermented grass silage (FOM) may serve as a more effective food source for earthworms, and thus could contribute positively to long-term soil structure and nutrient dynamics. Farmyard manure (FYM), despite boosting earthworm density by the end of the study, raised certain ecological concerns. Its application correlated with a decrease in overall fungal guild abundances, possibly due to pH increases that inhibit fungal growth. Additionally, the presence of saprotrophic fungi that thrive on dung may signal an imbalance or excess in organic inputs, which can disrupt microbial harmony and potentially introduce risks to crop health.

Third and finally, regarding economic performance, the results were also different across the various crops. Thus, regarding *Solanum tuberosum*, the treatment with compost (COM) showed the highest gross margin (46,000.44 €/ha), followed by the treatment with grass silage (FOM) (44,164.02 €/ha), while the farmyard manure (FYM) treatment exhibited an economic performance very similar to the control treatment, that is, no organic fertilization (BAU). In this sense, the gross margins obtained with FYM and BAU were 42,189.70 and 42,230.39 €/ha, respectively. On the other hand, regarding *Triticum spelta*, the FYM treatment was the only one that resulted in a higher gross margin compared to the control treatment (BAU, without organic fertilization). In this regard, the FYM treatment resulted in a gross margin of 488.48 €/ha, while the control treatment (BAU) showed a gross margin of 277.73 €/ha. Contrary to the results for potatoes, in the case of spelt, the FOM and COM treatments were the worst from an economic standpoint, both resulting in negative gross margins (-1,169.24 €/ha for COM and -1,554.11 €/ha for FOM).

Fig. 37. Earthworm abundancies during the period 2021 till 2023 for all treatments. BAU = no fertilizer, COM = compost, FYM = farmyard manure, FOM = silage grass.

Main Benefits of Incorporating Compost (COM) and Fermented Grass Silage (FOM) in Potato Crops

While all organic treatments demonstrated potential to enhance soil life and productivity in various ways, fermented silage grass (FOM) and compost (COM) appear to offer the most consistent benefits, without the drawbacks commonly associated with farmyard manure (FYM).

In this context—and bearing in mind that it may be premature to endorse any single practice as universally optimal without further supporting evidence—the incorporation of compost (COM) and fermented silage grass (FOM), at this stage and based on the results obtained, appears to yield the following benefits:

- Both treatments (COM and FOM) appear to increase the production of *Solanum tuberosum*.
- Both treatments (COM and FOM) show greater economic benefits in relation to potato cultivation.
- Fermented grass silage (FOM) appears to increase earthworm numbers, thereby contributing positively to long-term soil structure and dynamics.

9.4.

Potential drawbacks

The potato crop suffered from blight disease (*Phytophthora infestans*). Since the disease was spread all over the field with no differences between the treatments, apparently the applied farming treatments could not reduce the problem by an improved soil condition and plant health.

The farmer experienced more difficulties to spread and mix the silage grass on the field compared to the other fertilizers.

Case study 10a

Continental pedoclimatic region

Biocontrol of soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi by fungivorous soil fauna communities in conventional wheat cropping systems

Stefan Schrader^a, Christine van Capelle^a, David Alexander Bind^b, Martin Banse^a

^aThünen Institute of Biodiversity, Bundesallee 65, Braunschweig D-38116, Germany

^bFlächenAgentur Rheinland GmbH (FAR), Bonn, Germany

10a.1.

Study location

Case study 10a (CS10a) was situated within the Continental pedoclimatic region, in the German federal state of North Rhine–Westphalia, near Nideggen (50°42′ N; 6°29′ E) (Fig. 38). The soil at the case study site is classified as a Cambisol with a sandy loam texture. The location is characterised by a mean annual temperature of 8.8°C and an average annual precipitation of 600 mm.

Fig. 38. Location of case study 10a (CS10a).

10a.2.

Management practices implemented

Case study 10a was established on a field belonging to a commercial farm under long-term conventional management, which had employed reduced tillage (ploughless cultivation using a cultivator) for over ten years. The experimental design followed a non-randomised block layout with one control and two treatments, each replicated four times ($n = 4$) (Fig. 39). The experiment commenced in spring 2021 with the following crop rotation (Fig. 40): potato (2021), winter wheat (2022), and winter barley (2023). The experimental year was 2022. In 2023, agricultural management practices were applied uniformly across all plots in accordance with local farming practices.

The objective of case study 10a was to identify management practices that promote fungivorous soil fauna communities as antagonists of fungal plant pathogens (specifically *Fusarium*) in conventional wheat production, while applying reduced rates of fungicides and fertilisers. In addition, the study assessed the efficacy of a biostimulant and a plant adjuvant, in combination with an additive, in enhancing soil self-regulation processes and thereby contributing to *Fusarium* control. Within this context, the following treatments were implemented (Fig. 40):

- (1) **Control:** Reduced fungicide and fertiliser application.
- (2) **Treatment 1:** Reduced fungicide and fertiliser application with the addition of an additive (Kantor) and a plant biostimulant (Nutri-Phite Magnum S).
- (3) **Treatment 2:** Reduced fungicide and fertiliser application with the addition of an additive (Kantor), a plant biostimulant (Nutri-Phite Magnum S), and a plant adjuvant (Smart-Seed G).

The control, as well as Treatments 1 and 2, aimed to reduce external inputs in terms of plant protection products and fertilisers, with Treatments 1 and 2 additionally intended to support crop performance through the application of innovative products. Both treatments represented novel management practices introduced to the study area.

Fig. 39. Experimental design of case study 10a (left) and images of the experimental treatments (right).

Fig. 40. Management practices implemented and depiction of the objectives pursued in case study 10a.

10a.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Firstly, it is worth noting that the implemented treatments exhibited a delayed response to the management adjustments, with initial effects only becoming apparent in the year following their introduction.

With regard to soil biodiversity, the application of a plant biostimulant in combination with a plant adjuvant (Treatment 2) appeared to enhance collembolan diversity, potentially broadening the range of ecosystem services they provide. In contrast, fungal richness and diversity did not differ significantly among treatments. However, the use of biostimulants (Treatment 1) contributed to a reduction in the abundance of pathogenic fungi, indicating a positive effect on plant health. Accordingly, the combination of plant stimulants and additives (Treatment 2) may have partially compensated for the reduced fungicide inputs and supported the suppression of soilborne fungal pathogens (Muhorakeye et al., 2024).

In this context, several soil-derived variables were identified as explanatory factors for the variation in overall soil fungal community composition. These included indicators associated with ecosystem services related to nutrient cycling, such as cation exchange capacity (CEC), electrical conductivity (EC), base saturation (Bs), total nitrogen (Nt), soil pH, and the concentrations of magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca), potassium (K), and boron (B).

Regarding nematodes, their diversity increased significantly across all treatments from year one to year three.

In terms of crop productivity, contrary to common assumptions, the biostimulant did not lead to higher yields during the first two years, with crop yields remaining similar across all tested treatments.

Finally, in relation to economic viability, the control treatment (reduced fungicide and fertiliser application) consistently resulted in the highest gross margins, followed by Treatment 1 and Treatment 2, respectively (Fig. 41). This outcome was attributed to the increased costs associated with the application of the additive and biostimulant in Treatment 1, and the additional plant adjuvant in Treatment 2.

Fig. 41. Average gross margin by crop cycle and experimental treatment for CS10a, 2021–2023.

Therefore, taking all results into account, it can be concluded that the addition of biostimulants and a plant adjuvant significantly improves soil biodiversity, contributing to a reduction in the abundance of pathogenic fungi. This, in turn, reduces the need for synthetic fungicide applications, thereby limiting soil and water contamination. Moreover, it is expected that, in the longer term, such improvements in soil biodiversity will translate into enhanced overall soil health, leading to increased fertility and improved soil ecosystem services.

However, in the short term—as assessed in the present study—these treatments involving biostimulants and a plant adjuvant were not economically viable when compared to the control treatment (reduced fungicide and fertiliser application). This was primarily due to the fact that crop yields were similar across all three tested treatments, while implementation costs were higher for the treatments involving biostimulants and the plant adjuvant.

Main Benefits and Considerations of Applying Biostimulants and Adjuvants in Conventional Wheat Production

From an agroecological perspective, the application of biostimulants and adjuvants:

- Promotes soil biodiversity.
- Enhances soil ecosystem services.
- Enables a reduction in fungicide use, thereby limiting soil and water contamination associated with synthetic chemical inputs.

From an agroeconomic perspective, the application of biostimulants and adjuvants:

- Is currently not an economically viable alternative, as it involves higher input costs while achieving similar levels of productivity, thus reducing the gross margin.
- However, the improvements in soil biodiversity are expected to translate into increased crop yields in the medium to long term, potentially making this approach economically viable over time.
- Longer-term research is recommended to better assess the cumulative benefits and economic sustainability of these treatments.

10a.4.

Potential drawbacks

As no negative effects have been observed from the use of a biostimulant, either with or without additives, there is no reason to discourage their application; however, expectations regarding their short-term impact should remain moderate.

Case study 10b

Continental pedoclimatic region

Biocontrol of soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi by fungivorous soil fauna communities in organic potato cropping systems

Stefan Schrader^a, Christine van Capelle^a, David Alexander Bind^b, Martin Banse^a

^aThünen Institute of Biodiversity, Bundesallee 65, Braunschweig D-38116, Germany

^bFlächenAgentur Rheinland GmbH (FAR), Bonn, Germany

10b.1.

Study location

Case study 10b (CS10b) is situated within the Continental pedoclimatic region, in the German federal state of Saxony-Anhalt, near Trippigleben (52°32' N; 11°9' E) (Fig. 42). The soil at the site is predominantly of loamy sand texture. The location is characterised by a mean annual temperature of 9.2°C and an average annual precipitation of 546 mm.

Fig. 42. Location of case study 10b.

10b.2.

Management practices implemented

Case study 10b was conducted on land belonging to a commercial farm under long-term organic management, where ploughing was employed as the tillage system. The experimental design followed a non-randomised block layout, comprising one control and two treatments, each replicated four times (n = 4) (Fig. 43). The experiment commenced in spring 2021, with the following crop rotation (Fig. 44): potato (2021), winter wheat (2022), and mustard (2023). The experimental year was 2021. In both 2022 and 2023, organic management practices were applied uniformly across all plots, in accordance with local agricultural standards. This design facilitated the assessment of legacy effects of the treatments over time.

The objective of Case study 10b was to evaluate the biocontrol potential of fungivorous soil fauna communities against phytopathogenic fungi (*Fusarium* and *Alternaria*) and their associated mycotoxins, as well as to promote the establishment of such communities within organic potato cropping systems. In this context, the following treatments were implemented (Fig. 44):

- (1) **Control:** No undersowing, according to local practice.
- (2) **Treatment 1:** Strip undersowing in furrows.
- (3) **Treatment 2:** Broad undersowing in both furrows and on ridges.

Treatments 1 and 2 aimed to enhance the soil's intrinsic self-regulation processes by increasing plant diversity through two distinct undersowing strategies. The undersown crop mixture consisted of *Vicia sativa*, *Linum usitatissimum*, *Lolium perenne*, *Trifolium resupinatum*, and *Guizotia abyssinica*, applied at a seeding rate of 13.5 kg ha⁻¹. Both treatments represented innovative management practices newly introduced to the system.

Fig. 43. Experimental design of case study 10b (left) and images of the experimental treatments (right).

Fig. 44. Management practices implemented and depiction of the objectives pursued in case study 10b.

10b.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Firstly, with regard to soil biodiversity, it was found that undersown crops (Treatments 1 and 2) in organic potato cultivation promoted the abundance of microarthropods and the diversity of collembolan communities, thereby enhancing the ecosystem services they provide. In this context, it was also observed that, in general, undersown crops had a positive effect on both yield quality (grain moisture content) and yield quantity in the subsequent year. Broad undersowing (Treatment 2) proved more beneficial to both soil fauna and crop performance than strip undersowing (Treatment 1).

In relation to plant diseases, two phytopathogenic fungal species were identified: *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Alternaria alternata*. However, no significant differences in fungal DNA concentrations were detected among treatments. Mycotoxin concentrations remained below detection limits across all samples; thus, no conclusions can be drawn regarding the potential of the treatments to promote bioregulation of mycotoxins.

With respect to fungal diversity, both treatments—particularly broad undersowing (Treatment 2)—enhanced overall fungal diversity and may have the potential to reduce plant disease incidence. *Trichoderma atroviride*, in particular, responded positively to both treatments. This species is recognised as a promising biocontrol agent due to its capacity to promote antagonism and induce systemic resistance in plants (Brunner et al., 2005). Additionally, common saprotrophic fungi capable of decomposing xylan and cellulose (Domsch and Gams, 1969), as well as dung, may be favoured by broad undersowing (Treatment 2). While strip undersowing (Treatment 1) may promote fungi with cellulolytic properties and the ability to decompose wood (Okada et al., 1993; Giraldo and Grous, 2019), broad undersowing appears to foster a broader range of saprotrophs.

Regarding nematodes, both treatments (Treatments 1 and 2) were associated with an increase in nematode diversity from Year 1 to Year 3. However, the effect of year was more pronounced than that of treatment. Lastly, both treatments also increased both the abundance and diversity of earthworms.

Secondly, with regard to soil properties, it was found that both Treatment 1 (strip undersowing) and Treatment 2 (broad undersowing) led to an increase in soil NO_3^- concentrations, likely due to the inclusion of leguminous species, as well as in certain micronutrients. However, both treatments also resulted in a decrease in particulate soil organic carbon (POC) content.

In terms of crop yield, during the year 2021, in which potato was cultivated, both treatments led to a substantial reduction in productivity compared to the control.

The control treatment yielded an average of 10,090.63 kg/ha, whereas yields declined to 4,934.38 kg/ha and 4,965.63 kg/ha under Treatments 1 and 2, respectively. This reduction in yield, relative to the control, resulted in a negative gross margin for both treatments (Fig. 45). In 2022, when winter wheat was cultivated, yields were very low and comparable across all three treatments, with 1,200.83 kg/ha recorded for the control, 1,194.90 kg/ha for Treatment 1, and 1,226.15 kg/ha for Treatment 2. Among these, Treatment 2 resulted in the highest gross margin (Fig. 45). Finally, in 2023, when mustard was grown, yields were equally low across all treatments, leading to identical gross margins for the three experimental conditions (Fig. 45).

Fig. 45. Average gross margin by crop cycle and experimental treatment for CS10b, 2021–2023. *Control:* No undersowing, according to local practice; *Treatment 1:* Strip undersowing in furrows; *Treatment 2:* Broad undersowing in both furrows and on ridges.

Therefore, considering all the results, it was found that both tested treatments (strip and broad undersowing) led to an increase in soil biodiversity and, consequently, to an improvement in the associated ecosystem services. Furthermore, both treatments also demonstrated significant potential in reducing plant disease incidence. However, in comparison to the control, both treatments resulted in a substantial decrease in potato yield during the first year (2021), rendering them economically unviable in the short term. It should be noted, however, that one year is insufficient to draw definitive conclusions about the effectiveness of such practices. Consequently, longer-term research is recommended. In this context, it is anticipated that in the medium to long term, these treatments may become economically viable. Both treatments led to increased soil nitrate content, which could reduce the need for fertilisation in subsequent years. Likewise, both treatments significantly enhanced soil biodiversity, which is expected to contribute to improved soil fertility over time, potentially increasing crop productivity and, therefore, overall profitability. Another factor supporting the medium- to long-term viability of these practices is their promising effect on reducing plant diseases, which could lead to a significant decrease in plant protection costs. In conclusion, both treatments are expected to contribute to the maintenance or enhancement of long-term agricultural sustainability. Nevertheless, extended-duration studies are necessary to thoroughly assess the economic viability of these approaches.

Main Benefits and Considerations of Applying Undersowing in Organic Potato Cropping Systems

From an **agroecological** perspective, the application of undersowing:

- Promotes soil biodiversity.
- Enhances soil ecosystem services as a result of increased biodiversity.
- Reduces the incidence of plant diseases.
- Improves soil fertility by increasing nitrate concentrations.

From an **agroeconomic** perspective, the application of undersowing:

- Is currently not an economically viable alternative, as it leads to a considerable reduction in potato yield compared to the control treatment.
- However, the observed improvements in soil biodiversity and fertility are expected to result in increased crop yields in the medium to long term, potentially making this approach economically viable over time.
- Longer-term research is recommended to more accurately evaluate the cumulative benefits and economic sustainability of these treatments.

10b.4.

Potential drawbacks

Positive effects on microarthropods only occur in the year of cultivation of undersown crops; no legacy effects on soil fauna were detected. Based on the fungal and nematode investigations, we cannot conclude any drawbacks related to their use.

Case study 11

Continental pedoclimatic region

Potential of plant diversity to promote intrinsic soil self-regulation processes and to enhance fungivorous soil fauna communities in wheat cropping systems

Stefan Schrader^a, Christine van Capelle^a, David Alexander Bind^b, Martin Banse^a

^aThünen Institute of Biodiversity, Bundesallee 65, Braunschweig D-38116, Germany

^bFlächenAgentur Rheinland GmbH (FAR), Bonn, Germany

11.1.

Study location

Case study 11 (CS11) was situated within the Continental pedoclimatic region, in the German federal state of North Rhine–Westphalia, near the town of Nideggen (50°42' N, 6°29' E; see Fig. 46). The soil at this site is classified as a Cambisol with a sandy loam texture. The location is characterized by a mean annual temperature of 8.8 °C and an average annual precipitation of approximately 600 mm.

Fig. 46. Location of case study 11 (CS11).

11.2.

Management practices implemented

Case study 11 was established on a field of a commercial farm with a long-term history of conventional management, including reduced (ploughless) tillage. The experimental design consisted of a non-randomized block layout with one control and two treatment groups, each replicated across four plots ($n = 4$; see Fig. 47). The experiment was initiated in autumn 2020 following a rapeseed harvest, and the crop rotation (Fig. 48) proceeded as follows: winter wheat (2021), silage maize (2022), and winter wheat again in 2023. The year 2021 served as the primary experimental year. In 2022 and 2023, all plots were managed uniformly under conventional practices in accordance with local standards. This experimental approach enabled the identification of legacy effects of the treatments over time.

The objective of case study 11 was to evaluate the potential of increasing plant diversity within conventional wheat systems to reduce fungal diseases—particularly those caused by phytopathogenic *Fusarium* species—by promoting antagonistic, fungivorous soil fauna and enhancing soil self-regulatory processes. In this context, the following treatments were applied (see Fig. 48):

- (1) **Control:** Narrow seed rows (12.5 cm) with standard plant protection measures according to local practice.
- (2) **Treatment 1:** Extensive cultivation with wider seed rows (20 cm) and no plant protection.
- (3) **Treatment 2:** Diversified extensive cultivation with wider seed rows (20 cm), no plant protection, and clover undersowing.

Treatments 1 and 2 were designed to increase associated plant diversity within the crop system, with Treatment 2 also introducing sown plant diversity. Both treatments represented novel management practices for the study area.

Fig. 47. Experimental design of case study 11 (left) and images of the experimental treatments (right).

Fig. 48. Management practices implemented and depiction of the objectives pursued in case study 11.

11.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Firstly, it is important to note that the established treatments responded with a delay to the management adjustments. The first observable effects only appeared in the year following their implementation.

Regarding soil biodiversity, clover undersowing (Treatment 2) in wheat cultivation promoted soil fauna such as microarthropods (e.g., collembolans and mites), without negatively impacting yield quantity or quality. Moreover, the composition of the clover undersowing proved to be a critical factor: potential host plants for phytopathogenic *Fusarium* species—such as red and white clover—should be avoided.

In terms of fungal communities, several soil fungal taxa responded positively to both Treatment 1 and Treatment 2. Fungi associated with extensive farming using wide seed rows and no pesticide application (Treatment 1) included various taxa with potential ecological functions, such as biological control agents against plant pathogenic fungi (Lombard et al., 2015; Khairullina et al., 2023). Conversely, fungi positively associated with diversified extensive farming involving clover undersowing (Treatment 2) included common plant pathogenic genera such as *Fusarium*. However, it is worth noting that this genus also includes species acting as root endophytes and biocontrol agents against certain plant pathogens (de Lamo et al., 2020).

Regarding earthworms, Treatment 2 led to an increase in both the abundance and diversity of earthworm populations.

As for soil properties, both Treatment 1 and Treatment 2 resulted in increased soil nitrate content—particularly Treatment 2—compared to the control, thereby enhancing soil fertility.

In terms of crop yield, winter wheat in 2021 produced the highest yield under the control treatment (7,400 kg/ha), followed by Treatment 2 (6,325 kg/ha), and Treatment 1 (5,375 kg/ha). In 2022, with silage maize cultivation, Treatment 2 achieved the highest yield (36,951.11 kg/ha), followed by the control (34,151.11 kg/ha), and Treatment 1 (30,284.44 kg/ha). In 2023, when winter wheat was cultivated again, the highest yield was obtained under Treatment 2 (10,450 kg/ha), followed by the control (9,700 kg/ha) and Treatment 1 (9,600 kg/ha). Thus, while the tested treatments caused a slight decrease in winter wheat yield in the first year, by the third year, Treatment 2 had led to the highest winter wheat yield, suggesting its effectiveness also from a productivity standpoint.

Finally, regarding economic viability, in the first cultivation year (2021), neither Treatment 1 nor Treatment 2 proved economically viable, as both resulted in reduced gross margins compared to the control. However, by the third year (2023), the gross margin for Treatment 2 slightly exceeded that of the control, indicating that Treatment 2 can be considered economically viable (Fig. 49).

Fig. 49. Average gross margin by crop cycle and experimental treatment for CS11, 2021–2023. *Control*: narrow seed rows (12.5 cm) with standard plant protection measures according to local practice; *Treatment 1*: extensive cultivation with wider seed rows (20 cm) and no plant protection. *Treatment 2*: diversified extensive cultivation with wider seed rows (20 cm), no plant protection, and clover undersowing.

Therefore, based on the results, it was found that both tested treatments promoted biodiversity and, consequently, the associated ecosystem services. Additionally, they appear to be promising treatments for combating fungal pathogens. Finally, Treatment 2 was found to increase soil nitrate content, thereby enhancing crop productivity in subsequent years. In this regard, in the final year of the study, Treatment 2 resulted in the highest agricultural production, as well as the highest gross margin.

Main Benefits and Considerations of Applying Extensification (Wide Seed Rows) and Diversification (Clover Undersowing) in Conventional Wheat Production

From an **agroecological** perspective, the application of extensification and diversification:

- Promotes soil biodiversity.
- Enhances soil ecosystem services.
- Improves soil fertility.
- Combats fungal pathogens.

From an **agroeconomic** perspective, the application of extensification and diversification:

- Slightly increases winter wheat productivity, thereby improving economic performance.

11.4.

Potential drawbacks

The experiment showed that a promotion of antagonistic fungivorous soil fauna for bioregulation of *Fusarium* and its mycotoxins could not be demonstrated. Results indicated that both diversification treatments without pesticides can also lead into decreasing of putative beneficial saprotrophic fungi, and species of *Trichoderma*, which can act as biocontrollers of fungal and nematode plant pathogens and induce plant systemic disease resistance (Brunner et al. 2005 Yao et al. 2023).

Case study 12

Nemoral pedoclimatic region

Impact of agricultural management and tillage practices on soil biota

Merrit Shanskiy^a, Merit Sutri^a, Anne Põder^a

^aInstitute of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences, Estonian University of Life Sciences, 5 Fr. R. Kreutzwaldi St., Tartu 51006, Estonia

12.1.

Study location

Case study 12 (CS12) in the Nemoral region examined the impact of tillage practices on pesticide residues and soil fauna under no-till, reduced tillage, and conventional tillage systems in cereal fields, within both organic and conventional farming.

More specifically, the study was divided into two sub-activities (referred to as CS12 and CS12A):

- CS12 – management practices and soil biodiversity in reduced tillage and no-tillage cereal fields, with data collected in 2019 and 2020.
- CS12A – assessment of the impact of no-till and conventional tillage systems on soil biology and soil quality within organic and conventional farming, with data collection conducted from 2021 to 2023.

The **CS12 study** was conducted across five different locations in Estonia, with data collected from 10 fields (each with three replications) located in the counties of Viljandi, Põlva, Lääne-Viru, Saare and Pärnu (Fig. 50). In the Põlva and Lääne-Viru regions, the fields were managed used no-till practices, while in the other three regions, data was collected from reduced tillage fields. The mean annual temperature and precipitation for the locations were 7.7°C and 905 mm (Viljandi region), 8.5°C and 540 mm (Põlva), 6.9°C and 747 mm (Lääne-Viru), 9.2°C and 638 mm (Saare), and 8.8°C and 784 mm (Pärnu).

Fig. 50. CS12 locations for data collection in five regions in Estonia (reduced tillage and no-tillage fields).

The **CS12A** was located in southern Estonia, in the Nõo municipality (Fig. 51). The location is characterised by a mean annual temperature of 7.2°C, mean annual precipitation of 558 mm, and an annual potential evapotranspiration of 569 mm. The predominant soil type in the fields is Stagnic Luvisol (LP), accompanied by Gleyic Luvisol (Klg).

Field area. 1 = conventional farming under no-tillage; 2 = conventional farming under conventional tillage; 3 = organic farming under conventional tillage; 4 = field edge under grasses.

Fig. 51. Soil conditions for case study C12A (left), the plots (upper right), and location in Estonia (lower right).

12.2.

Management practices implemented

The study examined how different tillage systems affect soil biodiversity and pesticide residues, with the aim of encouraging the adoption of more sustainable soil management practices and gaining a better understanding of the challenges associated with these practices.

Fig. 52. Concept for CS12.*

*The field data collection for CS12 and CS12A did not include potatoes. Potato farmers were surveyed with a separate questionnaire survey in 2020.

The management practice in CS12 for four out of the ten fields was no-tillage in 2020. While there was some variation in the farmers approach for the other six fields, they were all classified as minimised tillage. The crop for all CS12 fields in 2020 was winter wheat.

Crop rotation differed for CS12A, in which cereal, legumes (peas), and alfalfa for fodder crop were in the rotation (Table 5 and Fig. 53).

Table 5. Crop rotation for CS12A.

Crop rotation	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3
Ctrl Agricultura convencional con laboreo convencional (CN)	Winter wheat	Winter wheat	Field pea
Conventional farming with no-tillage (CN no tillage)	Winter wheat	Spring wheat	Alfalfa
Organic farming with conventional tillage (OF)	Winter rapeseed	Winter wheat	Alfalfa

Fig. 53. Winter wheat in organic (left) and control plot (right) in July 2022 in CS12A.

12.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Firstly, with respect to soil biodiversity, neither treatments nor any soil-derived factors measured showed a relationship with the most dominant fungal taxa in the CS12A field experiment. However, a trend toward increased fungal diversity was observed in organic farming with conventional tillage, compared to conventional farming with conventional tillage (control). Furthermore, an increase in the abundance of fungi belonging to Hypocreales Incertae sedis was noted in uncultivated fields (field edges). The Didymellaceae family exhibited increased abundance under organic farming with conventional tillage, while the Mortierellaceae family was more prevalent under conventional farming with conventional tillage.

The abundance of pathotrophic fungi decreased in conventional farming without tillage but increased in organic farming with tillage. Additionally, a rising trend in the proportion of symbiotic fungi was observed in organic farming with tillage during the later years of monitoring. In general, no measured soil property was directly associated with the most dominant fungal taxa in the CS12A study. However, certain soil characteristics, such as plant-available phosphorus (Pav) and the second-largest soil aggregate fraction, were found to influence variation in fungal community composition, particularly toward the uncultivated field edges.

With regard to fungal biomass, the soil organic fraction—particularly organic matter (OM), total organic carbon (TOC), and total nitrogen (Nt)—was positively correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes bacteria. Particulate organic carbon (POC) showed a positive correlation with both Gram-positive bacteria and Zygomycota fungi. The content of plant-available manganese (Mnav) was positively correlated with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi. Additionally, higher soil bulk density (0–10 cm depth) was found to predict an increase in the relative abundance of the fungus *Acremonium furcatum*, as did elevated levels of plant-available phosphorus (Pav). In the organic field, a greater abundance of the endophytic fungal group Sebaciales, known for its beneficial effects on plant health, was observed. The differentially abundant fungal taxa under organic farming in the Nemoral region included the genera *Podospora* and *Rhizopydium*, as well as the order Sebaciales.

The CS12A study did not identify significant correlations between total microbial abundance and soil properties. The nematode community composition was significantly influenced by only three soil physicochemical parameters: magnesium (Mg), ammonium (NH₄), and molybdenum (Mo). NMDS plotting indicated that ammonium may have influenced nematode communities in 2023 (toward the end of the study). The other two parameters could not be clearly linked to any specific cultivation practice.

Molybdenum appeared to have an opposing effect relative to ammonium in shaping nematode communities. Crop yield did not show a significant relationship with nematode community composition.

Earthworm abundance and biomass were significantly lower in conventionally tilled fields compared to no-tillage and organic farming practices (Fig. 54 and 55). Frequent soil disturbance negatively impacted earthworm populations. Direct sowing and organic farming systems significantly promoted higher earthworm abundance and species diversity compared to conventional systems (Sutri et al., 2024). It can be presumed that direct sowing, the absence of synthetic chemicals, and the use of organic amendments supported earthworm populations.

Field edges, which often receive less direct agricultural intervention, had higher earthworm abundance and biomass compared to conventionally tilled fields, benefiting from the less disturbed and more diverse habitat. A comparison of no-till and reduced tillage fields in CS12 indicated higher earthworm biomass in no-till fields, although earthworm abundance varied between practices.

Fig. 54. Earthworm abundance on conventional farming under conventional tillage (CN), field edge under grass (FE), conventional farming under no-tillage (CN no-tillage), and organic farming under conventional tillage (OF) management, CS12A.

Fig. 55. Earthworm biomass on conventional farming under conventional tillage (CN), field edge under grass (FE), conventional farming under no-tillage (CN no-tillage) and organic farming under conventional tillage (OF) management, CS12A.

Secondly, concerning soil physicochemical properties, it was observed that no-tillage practices led to an increase in soil organic matter compared to conventional tillage practices, thereby increasing levels of organic matter (OM), total carbon (TC), particulate organic carbon (POC), and total nitrogen (Nt). Similarly, no-tillage practices also resulted in increased levels of plant-available phosphorus (Pav), as well as certain micronutrients (Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, Mo, and B). Therefore, no-tillage practices improve soil fertility and enhance carbon sequestration.

Thirdly, with regard to soil and water pollution, organic farming exhibited lower pesticide residue levels in wheat fields and supported greater biodiversity and species richness in Estonian agricultural soils compared to conventional systems. However, past agricultural practices and soil management also significantly influenced the current environmental state, with persistent pesticide residues found even in organically managed fields, and specific soil characteristics affecting earthworm communities (Rodríguez-Seijo et al., 2025). On the other hand, as is evident, organic farming practices result in a reduction in chemical fertilization use, thus decreasing contamination of both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems.

Fourthly, regarding productivity, the year 2020 was highly favourable for wheat production in Estonia, recording one of the highest average yields in a decade (the national average of 5,542 kg/ha; Statistics Estonia, 2025). The average wheat yield in the CS12 study for no-tillage fields was 6,675 kg/ha, and for reduced tillage fields, it was 6,850 kg/ha; however, the difference in average yield was not statistically significant.

In CS12, data from the previous year (2019) were provided by farmers for eight fields, in which rapeseed (seven fields; two no-tillage and five reduced tillage) and barley (one field, reduced tillage) were part of the crop rotation. The average yield of winter rapeseed was lower in no-tillage fields (2,400 kg/ha) compared to reduced tillage fields (2,898 kg/ha) in 2019.

The yield for winter wheat was highest in 2021, with yields for both no-tillage treatment (6,300 kg/ha) and conventional tillage under conventional farming (6,000 kg/ha) significantly exceeding the national average for that year (4,592 kg/ha; Statistics Estonia, 2025). Similarly, in 2022, the yield for winter wheat in the organic plot was 4,100 kg/ha, lower than the yield in the control plot (4,400 kg/ha), but still higher than the national average for organic wheat yields.

Finally, in terms of economic viability, the gross margin analysis for CS12 wheat fields in 2020 indicated that direct costs were higher for no-till fields (519 €/ha) than for reduced tillage fields (422 €/ha), resulting in lower gross margins on average for no-till (696 €/ha) compared to reduced tillage (821 €/ha). Wheat production proved more profitable than winter rapeseed production in 2019, due to lower input costs and higher yields in 2020. The application of no-till increased the average gross margin in the second crop cycle compared to the first cycle in 2019, suggesting a potential delay in the materialization of its benefits.

The gross margin analysis for CS12A compared the economic results of the three plots and their different crop rotations. The period of 2021–2023 was characterized not

only by high yields and a rapid increase in producer prices but also by highly volatile input prices. While revenues were higher for winter wheat in the case of no-till, input use was also considerably more intensive, resulting in a lower gross margin (900 €/ha) compared to conventional tillage under conventional farming for winter wheat (1160 €/ha) in 2021. Organic wheat production had a higher gross margin (1368 €/ha) than conventional wheat with conventional tillage (961 €/ha) in 2022. Organic tillage-based production had the highest gross margin for its 2021–2023 crop rotation of winter rapeseed, winter wheat, and alfalfa, followed by no-till under conventional farming with the rotation of winter wheat, spring wheat, and alfalfa.

In conclusion, considering all results, no-tillage and organic farming practices appear to offer significant environmental benefits, particularly in terms of biodiversity and long-term sustainability.

Benefits and Considerations of Adopting No-Tillage and Organic Farming Practices

- Organic farming increases fungal diversity, particularly in beneficial genera such as *Podospora* and *Sebacinales*, which are crucial for plant health.
- No-tillage and organic farming practices promote healthy and diverse earthworm communities, which are essential for soil health and nutrient cycling.
- No-tillage practices enhance soil fertility and structure by increasing organic matter, total carbon, total nitrogen, and particulate organic carbon.
- Organic practices contribute to the reduction of pesticide and synthetic fertilisers residues in soil and water, thus supporting environmental protection.
- Organic practices enhance soil nutrient availability, including plant-available phosphorus (P_{av}) and key micronutrients, promoting healthier plant growth.
- No-tillage practices may lead to a delayed economic benefit, as higher input costs may offset the initial savings from reduced chemical usage.
- **Tailoring tillage practices to field-specific conditions is essential** for achieving optimal biodiversity and economic benefits.

12.4.

Potential drawbacks

No-tillage. Transitioning to no-till farming requires substantial initial investment in specialised machinery and equipment. This financial barrier can be a significant drawback for small-scale farmers or those with limited resources. In no-till systems, farmers faced challenges with weed management, as the absence of soil disturbance can lead to increased weed pressure. This may necessitate the use of herbicides, which can have both environmental and economic implications. The lower gross margins for no-tillage in the cases studied indicate more intense and higher costs associated with inputs. In some parts of the field, observations in this study suggest that no-tillage can lead to soil compaction, particularly in heavy or poorly drained soils. These conditions can affect root growth and water infiltration, potentially reducing crop yields and impacting the earthworm communities.

Organic farming. Organic farming practices often require more labour for activities such as manual weeding, and yields tend to remain lower in comparison with other soil management systems.

Case study 13

Boreal pedoclimatic region

Increase of soil biodiversity through amendment of forest based organic material in potato crops

Krista Peltoniemi^a, Eija Pouta^a, Sari Livonen^a

^aNatural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Natural resources, Soil ecosystems, Latokartanonkaari 9, Helsinki FI-00790, Finland

13.1.

Study location

Case study 13 (CS13) was carried out in the Boreal pedoclimatic region (Finland), specifically in the Southwest Finland region, which is one of the main areas of early potato cultivation in Finland. Since the cultivation period of early potato in Finland is short, only 1.5–2 months, the soil remains bare for most of the year, making it vulnerable to erosion. Therefore, early potato farmers would benefit from management practices that help prevent nutrient and carbon loss as well as further damage.

The experimental field study site was located in Laitila (Fig. 56). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots involved in this case study are 60.915166°N and 21.681193°E. In 2021, the average temperature between April and the mid-June was 9°C, with a maximum temperature of 28°C. The total precipitation during this crop season was 119 mm. In 2022, the average temperature between April and mid-June was 8°C, with a maximum temperature of 21.5°C. The year 2022 was drier than 2021, with total precipitation between April and June amounting to 73 mm.

Fig. 56. CS13 location (to the left) and experimental plot (to the right).

13.2.

Management practices implemented

Case study 13 explores the potential of using organic forest-based soil amendments originating from side-streams of the forest industry. Three different sludges were tested: nutrient-poor fiber sludge (FB, also referred to as “zero fiber”), and two nutrient-rich sludges, composted pulp mill sludge (CPMS) and lime-stabilised pulp mill sludge (LPMS). CPMS and FS consists of cellulose fibres that are too short for the final product of the mill. The main difference between the materials is that CPMS was recovered from the mill’s wastewater treatment process containing phosphorus (P), nitrogen (N), and other nutrients added to the biological purification step to cut down oxygen demand of effluent waters, whereas FS is a nutrient-poor cellulose material from the pre-clarifier of cardboard machine process water, removed in a wire sieve as a semi-dry mass.

The experiment layout was a randomised complete block design with four replicates with a total of 12 plots (Fig. 56). Seed potatoes (early variety Timo) were planted (3000 kg ha^{-1}) each year in mid-April and crop was harvested in mid-June. Amendments were spread into the experimental plots once at the end of June 2020 and rates used for the sludges at their original moisture content were 50 t ha^{-1} .

Earlier results have shown promising positive effects of organic amendments processed from the side-streams of the forestry and pulp industry on soil structure and microbiology in arable soil (Rasa et al. 2021; Peltoniemi et al. 2023). The objectives were to test management practices allowing benefits to early potato soil, soil quality, and soil biodiversity.

13.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

During and after three years of monitoring, we found no evidence of effects of organic forest-derived soil amendments on prokaryotic, fungal or earthworm diversity and composition. Functional microbial gene abundances were also unaffected. There were some changes in the number and diversity of the nematode community due to organic amendments. However, these changes were likely to reflect the time of sampling.

The economic costs of both organic amendment application for the early potato farmer were higher than the income, so their use is not economically justified based on this experiment. Increased costs were not sufficient to be covered by the income from the harvest. Thus, the use of recycled soil amendment fibers in early potato production is not economically justified. However, by increasing the yield, it is possible to reach the break-even point for both, where the income covers the costs.

Based on the Results Obtained in the Present Study, the Following Recommendations Can Be Made:

- The use of side-stream based forest-derived recycled organic soil amendments in boreal early potato field cannot be directly recommended, since they produced extra costs for farmers because of the decreased gross-margins.
- The impacts of forestry-derived organic soil amendments in boreal early potato fields on soil were neutral; thus, their use does not cause harm to soil biology.
- Although short-term effects on soil function or biology could not be detected, long-term benefits may be observed, therefore further research in this field is recommended.

13.4.

Potential drawbacks

The coarse soil type, annual ploughing, and possibly also the frequent use of pesticides in the investigated early potato field provided a particularly challenging starting point for the investigation of soil biological diversity. The research period was short, and there were significant variations in producer prices for early potatoes. Therefore, the results might have been more reliable if a longer monitoring period had been implemented.

Case study 14a and 14b Boreal pedoclimatic region

Contrasting continuous plant cover and minimum tillage with inversion tillage in wheat fields

Krista Peltoniemi^a, Eija Pouta^a, Sari Livonen^a

^aNatural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Natural resources, Soil ecosystems, Latokartanonkaari 9, Helsinki FI-00790, Finland

14.1.

Study location

The experimental field for case study 14a (CS14a) was located in Kilpiä farm in Southern Finland, and for case study 14b (CS14b) was located in Tyynelä farm in South-Eastern Finland (Fig. 57). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots involved in this case study are 60.492519°N and 23.910014°E, and N 61° 6,629'; E 28° 43,782' for Kilpiä and Tyynelä farms, respectively. In both locations, the mean annual temperature is 5 °C, and the mean annual precipitation ranges from 650 to 700 mm.

Fig. 57. CS14a and CS14b locations.

14.2.

Management practices implemented

Case studies 14a and 14b explore the impact of sudden deep ploughing on soil biological diversity in the wheat fields under long-term organic farming with minimum tillage.

Deep ploughing as tillage method is thought to have negative impact on many soil organisms, particularly on fungi (Kabir et al., 1997; Wang et al., 2021), and on larger soil animals such as earthworms (Van Capelle et al. 2012; Crittenden et al. 2014). The replacement of ploughing by lighter tillage methods (minimum shallow tillage), accompanied by direct sowing, has become more common. Yet, ploughing is still often applied in organic farming to control weeds. The experimental layout for both CS14a (Fig. 58A) and CS14b (Fig. 58B) followed a randomized complete block design with four replicates, including a total of 8 plots. Plots with minimum tillage served as the control treatment, whereas treatment plots were mouldboard ploughed in spring before sowing in CS14a or in autumn after the harvest in CS14b (Fig. 58). CS14a and CS14b fields have not been ploughed since 2011 and 2017, respectively. Only minimum tillage was conducted in both sites before the experiment started. The main crop in the cropping cycle during the 3-year monitoring period included spring wheat in CS14a and winter wheat in CS14b during the first and third monitoring years. There was pea as a cover crop in both field sites in the second year.

Fig. 58. Experimental layout of A) CS14a and B) CS14b.

14.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

Microbial, fungal, nematode and earthworm communities developed under long-term organic farming with minimum tillage were notably resilient to changes due to ploughing. Beneficial changes in earthworm community achieved by minimum tillage were not lost even after three consecutive years of ploughing. The season affected the impacts of ploughing; autumn ploughing lowered the richness of nematodes and biomass of earthworms, which are important organisms in nutrient release and in pathogen control. In addition, C and N cycling related genes were lower due to autumn ploughing in organic winter wheat farming. Deep mouldboard ploughing as a tillage method in boreal organic wheat field is not a cost-effective method compared to minimum tillage, and thus cannot be recommended in well-functioning fields with balanced structural and functional conditions, as it did not significantly increase yield but increase costs for the farmer. If field must be ploughed for example to control weeds or to facilitate the accumulation of phosphorus load or prevent runoffs in the field, springtime ploughing is recommended.

In the crop rotation, ploughing generates both higher revenues and costs compared to minimum tillage on continuously covered fields. Ploughing results in greater overall yields than minimum tillage, which explains the higher revenues associated with this practice. However, ploughing is slower than minimum tillage, contributing to its increased costs. Despite the higher revenues from ploughing, minimum tillage produces greater gross margins in the crop rotation, making it a more economically justified option. The difference in gross margins between ploughing and minimum tillage is relatively small.

Based on the survey results, 61% of farmers expressed definite interest in future application of combined plant cover and minimal tillage. Soil moisture, structure, and weed control were key factors in assessing this practice. The opinions of **environmentally conscious peers were encouraging, yet they did not significantly influence** the adoption of the practice. Policy instruments, particularly subsidy opportunities, were seen as influential factors. Intentions to use the practice were largely shaped by past experiences and attitudes towards it. The belief that the practice could mitigate runoff also positively impacted farmers' interest in its adoption.

Based on the Results Obtained in the Present Study, the Following Recommendations Can Be Made:

- Deep inversion tillage with mouldboard ploughing in organic wheat farming cannot be recommended without well-judged reason (e.g. persistent weed or phosphorus runoff problems) since it is not a cost-effective tillage method for farmers.
- Impacts of occasional ploughing to soil organisms are not detrimental, thus however springtime ploughing in boreal cereal field should be promoted instead of autumn if possible.

14.4.

Potential drawbacks

Three-year monitoring time might not be enough to detect changes due to ploughing since weather conditions vary every year.

Case study 15

Boreal pedoclimatic region

Use of catch crop in farmed potato fields

Krista Peltoniemi^a, Eija Pouta^a, Sari Livonen^a

^aNatural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Natural resources, Soil ecosystems, Latokartanonkaari 9, Helsinki FI-00790, Finland

15.1.

Study location

Case study 15 (CS15) was carried out in the Boreal pedoclimatic region (Finland), specifically in the Southwest Finland region, which is one of the main areas of early potato cultivation in Finland. Since the growing period of early potato in Finland is short, only 1.5–2 months, the soil remains bare for most of the year, making it prone to erosion. Therefore, early potato farmers would benefit from management practices that could prevent nutrient and carbon loss, as well as further damage.

The experimental field study site was located in Laitila (Fig. 59). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots involved in this case study are 60.915166°N and 21.681193°E. In 2021, the mean temperature between April and mid-June was 9°C, with the maximum temperature reaching 28°C. The total rainfall during this crop season was 119 mm. In 2022, the mean temperature between April and mid-June was 8°C, and the maximum temperature was 21.5°C. Compared to 2021, 2022 was drier, with rainfall between April and June totalling 73 mm.

Fig. 59. CS15 location (to the left) and experimental plot (to the right).

15.2.

Management practices implemented

Case study 15 explores the potential of two different catch crops, phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia*) and a mixture of rye (*Secale cereale*) and Westerwolds ryegrass (*Lolium westerwoldicum*), to prevent physical and chemical damage, nutrient and carbon loss, and to promote soil biological diversity in an early potato field. Cover or catch crops are known to have beneficial effects on soil, such as increasing soil organic matter and available nutrient content, preventing soil erosion and nutrient leaching, suppressing weeds, and controlling soil-borne diseases (Shennan, 1992, Wyland et al., 1996, Ritter et al., 1998, Shrestha et al., 2002).

The experiment layout was a randomised complete block design with four replicates and a total of 12 plots (Fig. 59). Seed potatoes (early variety Timo) were planted (3000 kg ha⁻¹) each year in mid-April, and the crop was harvested in mid-June. Catch crops were sown in the field plots in mid-July after the harvest each year. The seed amount for phacelia and mix of rye and Westerwolds ryegrass were 15 kg and 175 kg ha⁻¹, respectively.

15.3.

Recommended management practices and main benefits

During and after three monitoring years, no evidence was found of the effects of two different catch crops on prokaryotic, fungal, or earthworm diversity and composition. The decline in nematode richness, coupled with the rise in overall nematode biodiversity, suggests that the catch crops might have potential to improve pest and disease management. However, the changes were likely more attributable to the time of sampling.

The economic costs of catch crop for the early potato farmer were higher than the income, so their use is not economically justified based on this experiment. Increased costs were not sufficiently covered by the income from the harvest. Therefore, the use of catch crops in early potato monoculture cannot be considered economically justified. However, by increasing the yield, it becomes possible to reach the break-even point for both, where the income covers the costs.

Based on the Results Obtained, the Following Recommendations Can Be Made:

- From an economical point of view sowing of tested catch crops in boreal early potato fields seems cannot be recommended since this was not profitable for farmers in short-term. However, farmers have an opportunity to utilise the current environmental compensation system when growing Phacelia as a catch crop after the harvest of early potatoes.
- Since potential beneficial effect of catch crops on pest and disease control in early potato field were observed, long-term investigations are recommended.
- It is recommended to explore benefits of catch crops in other than monocultures, i.e., more diverse crop rotations in boreal early potato farming.

15.4.

Potential drawbacks

The coarse soil type, yearly ploughing, and possibly also the frequent use of pesticides in the investigated early potato field made it an utterly challenging starting point for the investigation of soil biological diversity. The research period was short, and there were large variations in producer prices for early potatoes. Thus, the results might have been more reliable over a longer monitoring period.

References

IUSS Working Group WRB. 2022. World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition. International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Vienna, Austria.

IUSS Working Group WRB. 2022. World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition. International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Vienna, Austria.

Gómez-Armesto, A., Meno, L., Álvarez-Pousa, S., Fernández-Calviño, D., 2025. Development and effectivity of *Solanum sisymbriifolium* against potato cyst nematode under field conditions in soils from the southern Atlantic area. Crop Protection 188, 107036.

» <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2024.107036>

Ferris, H., Bongers, T., de Goede, R.G.M., 2001. A framework for soil food web diagnostics: extension of the nematode faunal analysis concept. Applied Soil Ecology 18, 13–29.

» [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1393\(01\)00152-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1393(01)00152-4)

Peltoniemi, K., Talgre, L., Autio, S., Känkänen, H., 2020. Chapter 10. Improving soil quality with cover crops. In: Soto-Gómez et al., Interactions between agricultural management and soil biodiversity: an overview of current knowledge.

» <https://soildiveragro.eu/publications/books/>

Zhang, J., Shen, C., Shang, T.H. & Liu, J.L. (2022) Difference responses of soil fungal communities to cattle and chicken manure composting application. Journal of Applied Microbiology, 133, 323–339.

» <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.15549>

van der Ploeg, J. D., Barjolle, D., Bruil, J., Brunori, G., Costa Madureira, L. M., Dessein, J., Drăg, Z., Fink-Kessler, A., Gasselin, P., Gonzalez de Molina, M., Grolach, K., Jürgens, K., Kinsella, J., Kirwan, J., Knickel, K., Lucas, V., Marsden, T., Maye, D., Migliorini, P., Milone, P., Noe, E., Nowak, P., Parrott, N., Peeters, A., Rossi, A., Schermer, M., Ventura, F., Visser, M., & Wezel, A. (2019). The economic potential of agroecology: Empirical evidence from Europe. Journal of Rural Studies, 71, 46–61.

» <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2019.09.003>

Muhorakeye, M.C., Namikoye, E.S., Khamis, F.M. et al. 2024. Biostimulant and antagonistic potential of endophytic fungi against *Fusarium* wilt pathogen of tomato *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. lycopersici. Sci Rep 14, 15365.

» <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-66101-1>

Brunner, K., Zeilinger, S., Ciliento, R., Woo, S.L., Lorito, M., Kubicek, C.P., Mach, R.L. 2005. Improvement of the fungal biocontrol agent *Trichoderma atroviride* to enhance both antagonism and induction of plant systemic disease resistance. *Applied Environmental Microbiology*, 71, 3959–65.

» <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.71.7.3959-3965.2005>

Domsch, K.H., Gams, W. 1969. Variability and potential of a soil fungus population to decompose pectin, xylan and carboxymethyl-cellulose. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 1, 29–36.

» [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717\(69\)90031-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717(69)90031-5)

Giraldo, A., Crous, P.W. 2019. Inside Plectosphaerellaceae. *Studies in Mycology*, 92, 227–286.

» <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simyco.2018.10.005>

Okada, G., Niimura, Y., Sakata, T., Uchimura, T., Ohara, N., Suzuki, H., & Kozaki, M. 1993. *Acermonium alcalophilum*, a new alkalophilic cellulolytic hyphomycete. *Transactions of the Mycological Society of Japan*, 34.

Brunner, K., Zeilinger, S., Ciliento, R., Woo, S.L., Lorito, M., Kubicek, C.P., Mach, R.L. 2005. Improvement of the fungal biocontrol agent *Trichoderma atroviride* to enhance both antagonism and induction of plant systemic disease resistance. *Applied Environmental Microbiology*, 71, 3959–65.

» <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.71.7.3959-3965.2005>

de Lamo, F.J., Takken, F.L.W. 2020. Biocontrol by *Fusarium oxysporum* Using Endophyte-Mediated Resistance. *Frontiers in Plant Science*.

» <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.00037>

Khairullina, A., Micic, N., Jørgensen, H.J.L., Bjarnholt, N., Bülow, L., Collinge, D.B., Jensen, B. 2023. Biocontrol Effect of *Clonostachys rosea* on *Fusarium graminearum* Infection and Mycotoxin Detoxification in Oat (*Avena sativa*). *Plants*, 12, 500.

» <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12030500>

Lombard, L., van der Merwe, N.A., Groenewald, J.Z. Crous, P.W. 2015. Generic concepts in Nectriaceae. *Studies in Mycology*, 80, 189–245.

» <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simyco.2014.12.002>

Yao, X., Guo, H., Zhang, K., Zhao, M., Ruan, J., Chen, J. 2023. *Trichoderma* and its role in biological control of plant fungal and nematode disease. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 14, 1160551.

» <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2023.1160551>

Rodríguez-Seijo, A., Pérez-Rodríguez, P., Arias-Estévez, M., et.al. & Calviño, D. F. 2025. Occurrence, persistence and risk assessment of pesticide residues in European wheat fields: A continental scale approach. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 138291.

» <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.138291>

Statistics Estonia. 2025. Statistical database. PMO281.

» www.stat.ee (22.04.25)

Sutri, M., Ivask, M., Kuu, A., Escuer-Gatius, J., Reintam, E., & Shanskiy, M. 2024. The effects of agricultural practices on earthworm communities in Estonia. *European Journal of Soil Biology*, 122, 103662.

» <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2024.103662>

Peltoniemi, K., Velmala, S., Fritze, H., Jyske, T., Rasi, S. and Pennanen, T. 2023. Impacts of coniferous bark-derived organic soil amendments on microbial communities in arable soil – a microcosm study. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*.

» <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fiad012>

Rasa, K., Pennanen, T., Peltoniemi, K., Velmala, S., Fritze, H., Kaseva, J., Joona J. & Uusitalo, R. 2021. Pulp and paper mill sludges decrease soil erodibility. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 50:172–184.

» <https://doi.org/10.1002/jeq2.20170>

Crittenden SJ, Eswaramurthy T, de Goede RGM, Brussaard L, Pulleman MM (2014) Effect of tillage on earthworms over short- and medium-term in conventional and organic farming. *Applied Soil Ecology* 83: 140–148.

» <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2014.03.001>

Kabir Z, O'Halloran I, Fyles J et al. (1997) Seasonal changes of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi as affected by tillage practices and fertilization: Hyphal density and mycorrhizal root colonization. *Plant and Soil* 192: 285–293.

» <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004205828485>

van Capelle C, Schrader S, Brunotte J (2012) Tillage-induced changes in the functional diversity of soil biota—A review with a focus on German data. *European Journal of Soil Biology* 50: 165–181.

Wang, Q., Liang, A., Chen, X., Zhang, S., Zhang, Y., McLaughlin, N.B., Gao, Y., Jia, S. (2021) The impact of cropping system, tillage and season on shaping soil fungal community in a long-term field trial. *European Journal of Soil Biology*. 102, 103253.

» <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2020.103253>

Ritter, W.F., Scarborough, R.W., Chirniside, A.E.M., 1998. Winter cover crops as a best management practice for reducing nitrogen leaching. *J. Contam. Hydrol.* 34, 1–15.

Shennan, C., 1992. Cover crops, nitrogen cycling and soil properties in semiirrigated vegetable production systems. *HortScience* 27, 749–754.

Shrestha, A., Knezevic, S.Z., Roy, R.C., Ball-Coelho, B.R., Swanton, C.J., 2002. Effect of tillage, cover crop and crop rotation on the composition of weed flora in a sandy soil. *Weed Res.* 42, 76–87.

Wyland, L.J., Jackson, L.E., Chaney, W.E., Klonsky, K., Koike, S.T., Kimple, B., 1996. Winter cover crops in a vegetable cropping system: impacts on nitrate leaching, soil water, crop yield, pests and management. *Agr. Ecosyst. Environ.* 59, 1–17.

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